

The Strength of Bone China and Hard Porcelain

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Abstract

This report addresses three questions: Is bone really used in bone china? Is bone china stronger than hard porcelain? Can synthetic materials be used in the fabrication of bone china? The report includes an extensive and detailed review of strength and related measurements of bone china, hard porcelain, and aluminous porcelain, enabling answers to the three questions to be given as “yes, usually, and yes.” A fracture mechanics model of porcelain strength is developed, based on microstructural toughening effects related to included particle size, and used to describe observed strength variations. Other fracture related phenomena in porcelain, such as nonequilibrium crack propagation and electrical breakdown are also reviewed. 300 references are included, covering 100 years of porcelain measurements.

Keywords: Bone China, Hard Porcelain, Fracture, Strength, Particle, Microstructure

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1 Introduction

There is no doubt that porcelain and bone china can lay claim to be the ultimate tests of the ceramic arts, sciences, and engineering in combination (Rado 1969; Kingery et al. 1976). The raw ingredients are derived from a variety of geological and biological sources, including clays, feldspars, quartz, alumina, and bone ash. Plastic deformation of the raw ingredients in particle form mixed with water is critical to the formation of shaped components in the ceramic “green” state. Heating at high temperatures in controlled environments, typically 1200–1400 °C in slightly oxidizing conditions, is required to transform the porous green bodies into dense fired ceramic bodies. The transformations take advantage of reactions that lead to vitrification and viscous sintering and eventually re-crystallization. Finally, the bodies are coated with amorphous glazes and re-heated, typically to 1000 °C, to form transparent layers or colored designs on the component surfaces. The results are components that are dense, hermetic, stiff, strong, translucent, electrically insulating, and smooth-surfaced. As a consequence, porcelain and bone china have been utilized for centuries in both artistic and engineering applications. Hence, the news in 2020 (WITN 2020) of the imminent closure of a major bone china ceramic manufacturing facility in Kinston, North Carolina (NC) was particularly noted by the author—the facility was geographically close, the last of its kind in the US, and hailed from a long tradition (Pence 1923). The author’s prior experiences, measuring microstructural effects in ceramic fracture (Cook 1985, 2015) lead as a consequence to several questions, including:

- 1 Is bone really used in manufacturing bone china?
- 2 Is bone china stronger than the porcelain ceramic to which it is often compared?
- 3 Can synthetic raw materials replace the “bone” in bone china?

Paralleling these questions were related discussions of alleged superiority of natural materials vs synthetic materials, e.g. spider silk stronger than steel (Oyen 2013), sustainable bamboo replacing concrete and other structural materials (Van der Lugt et al. 2006; Dixon and Gibson 2014), and claims (Brown 2020) that bones from grass-fed cattle make better plates!

The answer to question 1 was found easily and is “yes.” Bone is used in manufacturing bone china, both for mass-produced commercial components (e.g. tableware) and in fabricating unique artistic objects (e.g. figurines). Although, strictly, the bone used in both cases is “bone ash” in wet powder form, as noted in descriptions of the Kinston facility (Neer 2024) and the ingredient lists for bone china sculptures (Wardell 2020). Bone ash results from cattle bones, largely cleaned of organic matter, calcined at approximately 1000 °C, and milled to generate a white powder, consisting predominantly of hydroxyapatite, $3\text{Ca}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2 \cdot \text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$. Hydroxyapatite is a calcium phosphate, of which several play significant roles in bone china fabrication—an extensive review of the structures and properties of the many calcium phosphates is given elsewhere (Dorozhkin 2009). Answers to questions 2 and 3—is bone china stronger than porcelain? and can synthetic ingredients, calcium phosphates other than bone-derived hydroxyapatite, replace bone?—were surprisingly much more difficult to ascertain. These questions are the motivation for the current work, which provides an extensive review and critical assessment of the strength measurements, historical and recent, of bone china and hard porcelain.

The current work is divided into a further six major sections: The next, second, section provides a brief outline of the history, fabrication methods, and resulting microstructures of bone china and porcelain, including the role played by NC. The outline defines and explains many of the terms and concepts used in the succeeding sections that consider the structural characteristics and related mechanical properties, especially

strength, of bone china and porcelain. Specifically, the third section reviews the variations in density and elastic modulus with firing temperature and provides background for the fourth and fifth sections—extensive reviews of the variations in strength and strength-controlling included particles with firing temperature, density, relative porosity, composition, and microstructural scale. Many of the key works reviewed were published in the *Journal of the American Ceramic Society* and date back 100 years. Consideration of the effects of microstructural scale provides a foundation for the following, sixth, section, in which a modern-day fracture mechanics model for porcelain strength is developed. The model describes observed strengths and provides a framework for explaining many strength phenomena, including the differences between bone china and porcelain strengths and the sometimes apparently contradictory effects of the phases (e.g. quartz) present in the fabricated microstructures. A final, seventh, section considers the properties of bone china fabricated with “synthetic” raw ingredients as replacements for “natural” bone ash. An Appendix provides ancillary information relevant to strength considerations (e.g. acoustic emission, contact and non-equilibrium fracture, and dielectric breakdown). A complete list of references and data sources is provided.

2 History, Fabrication, and Microstructure

2.1 China

Building on a long tradition of ceramic fabrication using fired earthenware and stoneware, porcelain was developed in southern China during 700–1300 of the common era. Distinct from brown or grey, opaque, and porous earthenware and stoneware, fired porcelain objects were white, translucent, dense, and impermeable. These porcelain characteristics led to many fine ceramic pieces and porcelain ware was very popular throughout China and in a succession of Chinese imperial courts. The popularity generated commercial pressure leading to many refinements and improvements in porcelain fabrication and associated manufacturing. [An extensive, historical, view of the rise of porcelain in China and throughout the “old” world is given in Finlay (1998), with a focus on *cultural*, rather than technical, issues. See also Gerritsen (2020) and Yang (2021).] In modern terms, the starting ingredients of the Chinese porcelains were a mixture of white kaolinite clay and pegmatite rock, (the latter is a feldspar- and quartz-rich granite-like rock, sometimes known as “China stone” or “petuntse”). A simple fabrication scheme is shown in Figure 1(a), composition details are given below. The starting ingredients were ground, mixed, water added, and green-state shapes formed from the plastic mixture. Primary firing was at approximately 1350 °C for several hours, although there were often additional, lower temperature, pre and post “biscuit” and “glost” firings to form stiff bodies for ease of handling and glazing, respectively. The major center for Chinese porcelain production, Jingdezhen, is located in the mountains on a river, such that kaolin, pegmatite, water, firewood, and slopes for long kiln construction are all easily accessible.

Fabrication of the Chinese porcelains, also expressed in modern terms, relied on the formation of a eutectic liquid during firing such that densification of the green body was enabled by viscous flow of the constituents. The chemical reactions during firing are broadly as follows. (The temperatures are approximate and the processes overlap.) Much greater detail can be found in the overview of Carty and Senapati (1998) and the microstructural evolution studies of Lee and colleagues (Iqbal and Lee 1999, 2000; Lee and Iqbal 2001; Tarvornpanich et al. 2008ab). At 550 °C, the kaolinite clay ($\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 2\text{SiO}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) dehydroxylates to metakaolin ($\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 2\text{SiO}_2$) and subsequently at 950 °C metakaolin decomposes into a spinel-like structure ($\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{SiO}_2$) and amorphous silica (SiO_2). At 990 °C, the K feldspar orthoclase ($\text{K}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 6\text{SiO}_2$) from

pegmatite undergoes a eutectic reaction with the silica to form a liquid alkali aluminosilicate glass (K-Al-Si-O). The spinel-like structure reacts with the glass to form mullite ($3\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 2\text{SiO}_2$), initially as platelets at 1075 °C and then as prismatic needles at 1200 °C. Also at 1200 °C, quartz, crystalline SiO_2 , from pegmatite, begins to dissolve, and at 1400 °C quartz begins to transform into the SiO_2 polymorph of cristobalite. After cooling, the final microstructure consists of approximately 70 % volume fraction silica glass and 30 % volume fraction crystals—mullite needles, partially dissolved rounded quartz and a few cristobalite blocks, and irregular relict feldspar blocks, Figure 1(b). Although there are often minor chemical variations (e.g. Na substituting for K), the essential feature of porcelain is that the crystalline constituents of kaolin and feldspar are converted by a eutectic reaction to an amorphous liquid that enables densification. The resulting ceramic is white, as the kaolin and pegmatite are Fe free, translucent, as the body is glassy, and impermeable, as the body is dense. The surfaces of the fired ware are smooth, as a result of the incorporated glass, enabling fine superposed glaze designs. Chinese porcelain was thus a material extremely suitable for manufacturing domestic and court articles to handle foods and liquids and for creating delicate artistic objects, with the advantage of fabrication from local ingredients.

From a modern microstructural perspective, porcelain is a particulate composite material consisting of a glassy matrix encapsulating crystalline particles of quartz and mullite (and perhaps feldspar and cristobalite). The mechanical properties of the composite reflect the fact that the crystals are typically more resistant to fracture and deformation than the glass. Hence, composite porcelain is usually more resistant than glass to reversible deformation, contact damage, and crack propagation, which in modern materials properties terms are characterized as exhibiting greater elastic modulus, greater hardness, and greater toughness. As a consequence of the superior material properties, components made of porcelain usually also exhibit superior load carrying capability relative to glass components. The greater loads reflect a greater maximum supportable stress or greater strength of porcelain. It is clear from ancient porcelain objects, whole and sherds, that the strength was controlled by fracture and that the strength of a porcelain component is a brittle fracture strength, greater, but similar in nature, to that of glass.

2.2 Europe

The superior optical, glazing, and mechanical properties of porcelain materials meant that porcelain wares were suitable for transport and trade and hence by the 1600s a thriving export business of porcelain objects existed from China to Europe. The popularity of Chinese porcelain in Europe was almost a craze, especially at the European courts (Finlay 1998), such that the wares became known commercially as “white gold” (Ford 2020) and porcelain pieces became known colloquially as “China” pieces (Marchand 2020). The commercial impetus was powerful such that in the mid-1600s to mid-1700s, ceramic artisans across Europe attempted to replicate Chinese porcelain. Not knowing any of the material processing information above, European ceramists attempted to mimic the optical properties of porcelain: Combining glass frit with minor amounts of white SnO and other minerals, followed by firing at approximately 1000 °C resulted in dense materials commonly known as “soft-paste” (or artificial) porcelains (Barber 1907). These were not real porcelains as there was no eutectic chemical reaction on firing, just simple combination to form dense glass with some hard, stiff inclusions. However, the wares were very popular as they were white and translucent and the low firing temperatures enabled multi-colored glazes to be used in bright decorative patterns. They were referred to as soft as the firing temperatures were low and they were easily scratched. [Densified glass frit based soft porcelains and the related “Belleek” (Collins 1928) and feldspathic “dental porcelains” (Kelly 2004; Denry and Holloway 2010) are not considered in detail here. See Appendix Figure A1a and A1b for a fabrication

scheme and microstructure of such materials.]

After much experimentation and difficulty in approximately 1708–1710 German ceramists at Dresden, under royal patronage and coercion, were able to duplicate Chinese porcelain (Albers-Schoenberg 1960). The mix of raw ingredients they arrived at was essentially the Chinese formulation and reflects the now-familiar modern “triaxial whiteware” formulation (by mass fraction, wt %) (Kingery et al. 1976; Whyman 1994; Wardell 2020): 50 % kaolin, 25 % feldspar, 25 % quartz, Figures 1a and 1b. As in Jingdezhen, the German ceramists at Dresden were aided in their porcelain development by local supplies of kaolin and feldspar. Firing of the ground triaxial mixture at 1350 °C or greater led to the porcelain microstructure described above and (eventually, after the recipe escaped) the material became known as “German porcelain” or “hard-paste (or true) porcelain.” Hard here refers to the high firing temperatures and superior scratch resistance, similar to that of the Chinese porcelains.

In contrast, experimentation with porcelain fabrication by English ceramists in the 1700s was driven by stiff commercial competition between many potteries and based largely on variations and additions to soft paste formulations (Freestone 2000; Owen 2003; Ramsay et al. 2004). In particular, many potteries added gypsum ($\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) and bone ash (both white) to the frit and fine-grained “ball clay” (kaolin + silica, titania, and iron oxide impurities, also known as “blue clay”) to the body before firing. The results were artificial porcelains, sometimes known as “bone ash porcelains,” as there was a substantial (20 %–40 %) bone ash content in the frit [Copeland 1992]. In the late 1700s, the Spode pottery (Roden 1997) implemented processing variations that included (i) large amounts of bone ash added directly to the raw ingredients (rather than pre-calcined with a frit) and (ii) “Cornish” stone, a feldspar rich rock similar to China stone, added to the raw ingredients (instead of glass frit). The Spode formulation became the basis for modern day “bone china” (Wardell 2020) (wt%): 50 % bone ash, 25 % feldspar, 25 % kaolin, mixed, formed, and fired at approximately 1200 °C, Figures 1c and 1d. Bone china wares were white, translucent, and had similar mechanical properties to the Chinese and other hard paste porcelains (hence the “china” name, although it was also known as “English” porcelain). Bone china was very successful commercially such that by the mid-1800s almost all English potteries were using the above bone china formulation for high-end products. Although the exact origin of bone china in England is debated (Copeland 1991; Freestone 2000), bone china was never manufactured in China.

Fabrication of bone china, in common with hard porcelain, relied on the formation of a eutectic liquid during firing such that densification occurred by viscous flow. The chemical reactions during firing for bone china are as follows. Much greater detail can be found in the microstructure evolution studies of Weyl (1941ab), St. Pierre (1954, 1955, 1956), Jordery et al. (1998), Iqbal et al. (2000ab), Kara and Stevens (2002abcd), and Kim et al. (2015, 2018). As in hard paste porcelain, at 550 °C, the kaolinite ($\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 2\text{SiO}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) dehydroxylates to metakaolin ($\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 2\text{SiO}_2$) and subsequently at 950 °C the metakaolin decomposes into a spinel-like structure ($\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{SiO}_2$) and amorphous silica (SiO_2). However, in bone china, two intermediate reactions occur. At 800 °C, the hydroxyapatite [$3\text{Ca}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2 \cdot \text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$] of the bone ash dehydroxylates and decomposes into beta tri-calcium phosphate [$\beta\text{-TCP}$, $\beta\text{-Ca}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$] and lime (CaO). At 900 °C, the lime reacts with the metakaolin to form the Ca feldspar anorthite ($\text{CaO} \cdot \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 2\text{SiO}_2$). At 990 °C, also as in hard paste porcelain, the initial alkali feldspar ($\text{K}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 6\text{SiO}_2$) undergoes a eutectic reaction with the silica and lime to form a liquid alkali calcium aluminosilicate glass (K-Ca-Al-Si-O). If the firing temperature is high enough, some mullite may form as in hard paste porcelain. After cooling, the final microstructure consists of approximately 30 % volume fraction glass and 70 % volume fraction crystals—dendritic anorthite, partially dissolved spheroidal $\beta\text{-TCP}$ and (perhaps) a few mullite needles.

Although there are often minor chemical variations here, too (e.g. added quartz, Na substitution), the essential feature of bone china is that the crystalline constituents of hydroxyapatite, kaolin, and feldspar are converted by a eutectic reaction to an amorphous liquid that enables densification. Bone china is thus a true porcelain, with all the porcelain attributes: white, translucent, impermeable, smooth, with mechanical properties superior to glass. From a modern perspective, bone china is close to a glass-ceramic in microstructure. Of course, the constituents of the bone ash porcelains can follow a similar, if more restricted, reaction path to that above. The large amounts of bone ash used in these earlier materials suggests this was so and that mid-1700s English potters were implementing this process in commercial wares. The distinction between bone china and bone ash porcelains can therefore sometimes be unclear.

2.3 America

The development of porcelain and bone china in England in the 1700s was accelerated by a critical contribution from the American “colonies,” and from the Cherokee natives of NC in particular: kaolin. In the mountainous west of NC, a band of the Cherokee nation mined a mica-containing clay they called unega (“white”) for manufacture of pipes and pottery and stucco on buildings. Early 1700s English potters in the colonies made a form of porcelain from this clay and, realizing the implications, took news of the clay back to England. By the mid-1700s a patent was issued in England for manufacture of ceramic ware using a starting mixture containing 50 % Cherokee clay, specified as “unaker,” with balance soda-lime glass frit to form a soft-paste porcelain (Ramsay et al. 2004). In the late 1700s, the Wedgwood potteries commissioned an expedition from the English settlement of Charleston, South Carolina (SC) to the native town of Cowee on the Little Tennessee river in western NC (about 200 miles). After much bargaining and a harrowing return journey, the expedition transported five tons (about 3 m³) of unaker back to England, where it was used by Wedgwood for several years in developing new lines of pottery and by a few other established potteries in manufacturing clay-rich near-porcelains (Freestone, 2000; Ramsay et al. 2004, 2008; Owen et al. 2018). There are many popular accounts of the native NC kaolin mines and the Wedgwood-sponsored clay acquisition expedition (Anderson 1986, 2006; Ellison 2010; Cherokee Images 2017; Bouknight 2019), and a roadside sign, shown in Figure 2, marks the mine locale just outside of Cowee. What is less well known, but perhaps might be expected, is that finished pottery wares were exported at the same time in the other direction, from England to the Americas. Soft-paste porcelain sherds, traceable to English potteries of the mid-1700s, have been unearthed from early settlement sites in Charleston, SC (Owen et al. 2011). (Similarly, English stoneware and a few porcelain pieces of the early 1800s has been unearthed in Cape Town, South Africa, Klose and Malan 2000.)

By the late 1800s, the quality and locations of kaolin and feldspar deposits in the western NC Blue Ridge mountains were well established (Holmes and Hill 1895). The need for raw ingredients to manufacture ceramic wares (Russell and Mohr 1947; Russell et al. 1956) was at least partially driven by the need for insulators in the burgeoning electricity businesses (Tod 1977; Myers 2010). In the early 1900s, technical studies in ceramics manufacture showed the NC clays and feldspars (“Carolina stone”) to be the equal of the English clays and Cornish stones to which they were compared (Hemsteger and Stief 1926; Monack 1931; Weis and Boyd 1937), although different in origin (Leech 1925). (Ironically, porcelain was being manufactured in China at this time using “American methods,” Leibson 1929). NC kaolin clay was used frequently in fundamental ceramics studies, including those investigating glazes (Sproat 1923; Thompson 1931), engobes (McVay and Parmelee 1937), glassy phases in whitewares (Shelton 1935; Shelton and Meyer 1938; Austin and Brooks 1941), and alternative formulations, e.g. the extensive studies of Koenig using

syenite as a replacement for feldspar (Koenig 1936, 1937, 1939ab, 1940, 1942, 1955; Wilson and Koenig 1958) and those of Thiess using steatite and cordierite bodies (Thiess 1937, 1943). By far the most visible early application of the NC kaolins, however, was by the Ceramic Research Laboratory of the Tennessee Valley Authority (TVA). Established in 1934, the Laboratory had the three fold aim of developing the usefulness of NC kaolins and feldspars for ceramic manufacturing in the Valley, assisting in the development of high temperature electrically heated kilns, and performing basic research on the production of vitreous dinnerware made from American materials. An extensive series of reports by Gould, Hedquist, and colleagues (1937, 1939, I–VII) detailed the workings and outputs of the Laboratory, which, although constructed on a near-industrial scale and had a very experienced practical leader in Gould (e.g. work on plates in 1937), was short-lived, closing in 1940 (TVA 2021). A subsequent report on manufacturing china clay opportunities in NC (Etheridge and Stuckey, 1941) appears to show that the Laboratory met all three of its aims. In 2016, a fire after a lightning strike near the current TVA site at Norris, Tennessee, just north of the Blue Ridge, revealed a tunnel kiln used by the Laboratory that had lain dormant for nearly 80 years (Gaines 2019). Mining of quartz and feldspar continue today around Spruce Pine, NC in the Blue Ridge (Swanson and Veal 2010) and, to close this brief history, Spruce Pine feldspar was a key ingredient in the bone china manufactured in Kinston NC.

3 Observations: Density and Elastic Modulus

3.1 Density

Comparison of the strengths of bone china and hard porcelain begins with considerations of material density ρ (mass/volume) and elastic Young’s modulus E . Specifically, the variations in these two quantities with fabrication temperature provide a necessary basis for comparison of strengths. Fabrication temperature here will be taken as the peak temperature attained during a firing cycle for a material. Usually, peak temperatures were > 1000 °C, firing cycles were longer than 10 h, and peak temperatures were maintained for several hours within a cycle. Firing cycles, especially in earlier studies, were often terminated by the observed slumping of calibrated pyrometric cones. Figure 3 shows graphs of the observed variations in post-fired density as a function of fabrication temperature for representative examples of (a) hard porcelain and (b) bone china, using data derived from the published works cited (all data sources are listed in figure captions). The graphs are drawn to the same scale and the shaded bands are guides to eye of the temperature domain 1250–1300 °C. (The density range spans wet clay, ≈ 1.6 Mg m⁻³, to crystalline quartz, 2.65 Mg m⁻³. \approx means “approximately equal to.”) Symbols represent mean values of reported density and lines connecting symbols are guides to the eye; where available, uncertainties are indicated as bars.

There are clear similarities and differences in the variations of density with fabrication temperature for bone china and hard porcelain. In both cases, the fired density passes through a maximum as a function of fabrication temperature. The temperatures to obtain peak density are ≈ 1300 °C for hard porcelain and less, ≈ 1200 °C, for bone china. The observed peak densities are quite different: ranging between 2.40–2.50 Mg m⁻³ for hard porcelain and a greater range, between 2.05–2.65 Mg m⁻³ for bone china. A material related to hard porcelain is aluminous porcelain, in which alumina (Al₂O₃) particles replace some fraction of quartz (SiO₂) particles in the hard porcelain ingredients (Austin et al. 1946; Schroeder 1978; Liebermann 2001a; Kim, K 2020; Kim, T 2020). The alumina particles impart some mechanical advantages and aluminous porcelain is the basis of the electrical insulator industry (Pence 1923; Treischel 1923). [The advocacy articles

of Liebermann (2000, 2001ab, 2003, 2017) and Liebermann and Schulle (2002) somewhat confusedly extol the mechanical advantages.] See Appendix Figure A1c and A1d for a fabrication scheme and microstructure of aluminous porcelain. See Appendix Figure A2 for variations of density with fabrication temperature for representative aluminous porcelains; the variations are similar to those of hard porcelains. For bone china and both porcelain materials the maxima in density as a function of fabrication temperature arise from competitions between densification and “bloating” (Riley 1951). On increases in temperature viscous sintering leads to densification of the green ceramic compact through removal of pores and interstices, and thus removal of the associated internal surface energy. However, increases in temperature also lead to the exsolution of gases, e.g. H_2O , O_2 , CO_2 , and SO_2 , within the compact from the decomposing and reacting green constituents, e.g. $\text{CaCO}_3 \rightarrow \text{CaO} + \text{CO}_2$, $6\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 \rightarrow 4\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{O}_2$. These reaction processes lead to bloating through the development of gaseous internal pore pressure. Overall, densification dominates at low temperatures and bloating dominates at high temperatures, leading to maxima in density that depend on melt viscosity, green-state composition, and furnace temperature ramp rates (Riley 1951; Khokhel’ 1958; Katsuki et al. 2020).

Figure 4 highlights the differences in density behavior for the three porcelain materials in a composite plot of observed peak coordinates (density, temperature). In Figure 4a different symbols represent observations from different materials and studies, similar to the studies of Figure 3; bars indicate uncertainties where available. It is apparent that all three porcelain materials exhibit considerable variation in peak density behavior, although broad trends are clear. The differently shaded rectangles in Figure 4a indicate the bounds of the 17 % and 83 % quantiles in peak density and fabrication temperature for each porcelain type. (2/3 of observations. Note that the density and temperature coordinates were analyzed independently.) The rectangles, indicating characteristic densification behavior, are repeated in Figure 4b: Peak density for bone china is typically observed at the lowest fabrication temperature and exhibits the greatest range. Peak density for hard porcelain is observed at a greater fabrication temperature but exhibits the smallest range. The peak density and related fabrication temperature ranges of bone china and hard porcelain overlap. Peak density and fabrication temperatures for aluminous porcelain are greater than those of hard porcelain and there is typically no overlap in observations. (The density of crystalline Al_2O_3 , corundum, often referred to as “sapphire,” is $\approx 4 \text{ Mg m}^{-3}$, thus partly explaining the greater density of aluminous porcelain.) Quantiles of observed fabrication temperature and peak density for each porcelain type are given in Table 1.

Figure 4 also highlights a major difficulty in assessing potential differences in the mechanical properties of bone china and hard porcelain. Are such assessments to be performed at a fixed fabrication temperature? At a fixed density? Or at a defined peak condition? The following section considers elastic modulus behavior taking note of these questions.

3.2 Elastic Modulus

Figure 5 shows the behavior of density ρ and Young’s modulus E on fabrication for three hard porcelain materials, using data derived from the published works cited. Different material systems are represented in Figures 5a, b, and c, which consist of two panels each and show the variations of ρ , upper panels, and E , lower panels, as a function of fabrication temperature. The panels are arranged in order of decreasing fabrication temperature domain. The upper panels display maxima in density as a function of temperature as observed in Figure 3. The variations in moduli shown in the lower panels are similar and display maxima in moduli at temperatures approximately the same as those for maximum density. (The Young’s modulus of silicate glasses is $\approx 60 \text{ GPa}$.) Temperature can be eliminated from the sets of panels in Figures 5a, b,

and c to yield the modulus-density trajectories shown in Figures 5d, e, and f, respectively. Arrows indicate the direction of fabrication temperature increase from the lowest temperature; in all cases the trajectories are hysteretic, suggesting that modulus was not solely determined by density, but also influenced by phase assemblage and microstructure. Note that the parameter $(E/\rho)^{1/2}$ characterizing acoustic velocity changes weakly along the trajectories and differs little between the materials. The distinct “ringing” or “resonance” of porcelain wares (Whyman 1994; Finlay 1998) is thus probably due to the absence of pores (or cracks, see below) and other density fluctuations that lead to acoustic damping, rather than increased sound velocities and resonant frequencies.

Figure 6 shows the differences in modulus behavior for the three porcelain materials in a composite plot of observed peak coordinates (modulus, density), similar to that of Figure 4. In Figure 6a different symbols represent observations from different materials and studies, similar to the studies of Figure 5; bars indicate uncertainties where available. It is apparent that all three porcelain materials exhibit weak variations in peak modulus behavior and the broad behavior is clear. The differently shaded rectangles in Figure 6a indicate the bounds of the 17 % and 83 % quantiles in peak modulus and density for each porcelain type. (2/3 of observations. Modulus and density coordinates were analyzed independently. The sets of density values differed slightly from those of Figure 4.) The rectangles, indicating characteristic modulus behavior, are repeated in Figure 6b: Peak Young’s modulus values for bone china and hard porcelain overlap completely, although, as in Figure 4, bone china is somewhat more dense and the ranges of values are different. Peak modulus and density values for aluminous porcelain are greater than those of hard porcelain and there is typically no overlap in observations, also as in Figure 4. (The characteristic Young’s modulus of crystalline Al_2O_3 , corundum or sapphire, is ≈ 400 GPa, thus partly explaining the greater modulus of aluminous porcelain.) Quantiles of observed Young’s modulus for each porcelain type are given in Table 1.

In many studies only behavior along the increasing temperature branch of a modulus-densification trajectory was observed in detail (i.e. parallel to the arrows in Figure 5). Comparison of behavior along such trajectories for the different materials shows the similarity of elastic modulus development during fabrication. Figure 7 is an expanded logarithmic composite plot of modulus and density for the three porcelain materials, showing the development of ceramic characteristics on fabrication temperature increases. Different symbols represent observations from different materials and studies, similar to Figure 6, using data derived from the published works cited. Progression from the green state to the fully fired state is from left to right, parallel to the arrow. The shaded rectangles are repeated from Figure 6. It is clear that bone china and hard porcelain follow a similar development trajectory, progressing from the lower left, indicating green states, toward the shaded rectangles, indicating optimally fired states. The similarity is highlighted by the gray line empirical guide to the eye of slope 3, $E \sim \rho^3$. (\sim means “varies as.”) It is also clear that aluminous porcelain follows a slightly different trajectory, shown in the upper right. The similarity of trajectory slopes makes clear the dominant effects of density on determining material elastic moduli. However, a more important point to be gained from Figure 7 is that unbiased comparisons of elastic modulus values for bone china and hard porcelain should be performed at similar densities, or at similar points in the modulus-density trajectory.

4 Observations: Strengths and Flaws

4.1 Strengths

Figure 8 shows plots of the observed variations in post-fired strength as a function of fabrication temperature for representative examples of (a) hard porcelain and (b) bone china, using data derived from the published works cited. The plots are drawn to different scales and the shaded bands are guides to eye of the temperature domain 1250–1300 °C. Symbols represent mean values of reported strengths and lines connecting symbols are guides to the eye; where available, uncertainties are indicated as bars. The plots are similar to those for density, Figures 3 and A2, and elastic modulus, Figure 5. As for density and modulus, there are clear similarities and differences in the variations of strength with fabrication temperature for bone china and hard porcelain. In both cases, the strength passes through a maximum as a function of fabrication temperature. The temperatures to obtain peak strength are ≈ 1300 °C for hard porcelain and less, ≈ 1200 °C, for bone china. The observed peak strengths are quite different: ranging between 40–100 MPa for hard porcelain and a greater range, between 75–200 MPa for bone china.

Figure 9 highlights the differences in peak strength behavior for the three porcelain materials (including aluminous porcelain) in a composite plot of observed peak coordinates (strength, temperature), using data derived from the published works cited. In Figure 9a different symbols represent observations from different materials and studies, similar to Figures 4 and 6; bars indicate uncertainties where available. It is apparent that all three porcelain materials exhibit considerable variation in peak strength behavior, although a broad pattern is clear. The differently shaded rectangles in Figure 9a indicate the bounds of the 17 % and 83 % quantiles in peak strength and fabrication temperature for each porcelain type. (2/3 of observations. Note that the strength and temperature coordinates were analyzed independently. The sets of temperature values differed slightly from those of Figure 4.) The rectangles, indicating characteristic strength behavior, are repeated in Figure 9b: Peak strength for bone china is typically observed at a lower fabrication temperature and exhibits a greater range than hard porcelain. The peak strength ranges and related fabrication temperature domains of bone china and hard porcelain overlap. Peak strength and fabrication temperatures for aluminous porcelain are greater than those of hard porcelain and there is a weak overlap in observations. Quantiles of observed peak strength for each porcelain type are given in Table 1.

Figure 10 is a plot of empirical distribution functions (edf) of the peak strength observations for bone china, hard porcelain, and aluminous porcelain from Figure 9a. The edf was formed by ranking the N peak strength observations for each material from least to greatest and assigning each an index i from 1 to N , such that σ_1 is the least strength and σ_N is the greatest. The quantity $Pr(i) = (i - 0.5)/N$ is then formed for each value of i . Elimination of i from the parametric set $[\sigma(i), Pr(i)]$ gives the discrete function $Pr(\sigma)$ that is the strength edf. $Pr(\sigma)$ gives the probability that a randomly selected member of the set has a strength less than σ . More details and examples can be found elsewhere (Cook 2023). The dashed lines in Figure 10 indicate the $Pr = 17\%$ and 83% probability levels. The number of peak strength observations in each edf are $N = 67$ (hard porcelain), $N = 34$ (bone china), and $N = 24$ (aluminous porcelain). Each peak strength value was determined from the outcome of many individual strength tests (as in Figure 8) such that Figure 10 represents information from over 2000 strength measurements (that constitute almost the complete population of found measurements). It is recognized that as the peak strengths reflect observed and reported quantities they are not strictly random variables that are independent and identically distributed (iid, Cook 2023). Nevertheless, Figure 10 reiterates the information in Figure 9 in more detail: the ranking process reduces the “scatter” such that the separations of the strength values for the three materials are now

clear. The separations are particularly clear between the 17 % and 83 % probability levels, showing that the bounds and the median strengths, the $Pr = 50$ % probability strength quantiles, are distinct. Figure 10 provides numerical data for further analysis.

Figure 11 shows the behavior of density ρ and strength σ on fabrication for two hard porcelain materials, using data derived from the published works cited. Different material systems are represented in Figures 11a and b, which consist of two panels each and show the variations of ρ , upper panels, and σ , lower panels, as a function of fabrication temperature, similar to elastic modulus considered in Figure 5. The upper panels display maxima in density as a function of temperature as observed in Figures 3, 5, and 8. The variations in strength shown in the lower panels are similar and display maxima in strength at temperatures approximately the same as those for maximum density. Temperature can be eliminated from the sets of panels in Figures 11a and b to yield the strength-density trajectories shown in Figures 11c and d, respectively. Arrows indicate the direction of fabrication temperature increase from the lowest temperature; the trajectories are weakly hysteretic, suggesting that strength was not solely determined by density, but also influenced by phase assemblage and microstructure. Note that the parameter σ/ρ characterizing specific strength changes weakly along the trajectories and differs somewhat between the materials.

Figure 12 is an expanded logarithmic composite plot of strength and density for the three porcelain materials, showing the development of ceramic characteristics on fabrication temperature increases. Different symbols represent observations from different materials and studies, similar to Figure 7, using data derived from the published works cited. Progression from the green state to the fully fired state is from left to right, parallel to the arrow. The shaded rectangles are determined from information in Figures 4 and 9. Although there is greater scatter relative to the elastic modulus variation of Figure 7, it is clear that bone china and hard porcelain follow a similar strength development trajectory, progressing from the lower left, indicating green states, toward the shaded rectangles, indicating optimally fired states. The similarity is highlighted by the gray line empirical guide to the eye of slope 3, $\sigma \sim \rho^3$. It is also clear that aluminous porcelain follows a slightly different trajectory, shown in the upper right. The similarity of trajectory slopes makes clear the dominant, but not totally controlling, effects of density on determining material strengths. Figure 13a replots the rectangular regions from Figure 12, making clear the peak strength variations observed for porcelain materials in terms of density. Figure 13b combines information from Figures 6 and 9 to plot similar rectangular regions delimiting the 17 % and 83 % quantiles of observed failure strain, given by $\varepsilon_f = \sigma/E$, where σ and E are the peak values for a material. Quantiles of observed peak strength and failure strain for each porcelain type are given in Table 1.

Figures 9, 10, 12, and 13 and Table 1 address question [2] stated previously: is bone china stronger than hard porcelain? Simple inspection of the edf variations in Figure 10 suggests that the answer to this question is “yes,” although the observed strength distributions overlap considerably. In more detail, the median peak strengths, the 50 % quantiles, of bone china and hard porcelain are 96 MPa and 65 MPa, respectively, a difference of 31 MPa. The differences between the 83 % and 17 % quantiles for the materials are 67 MPa and 47 MPa. The average half-span is thus approximately 29 MPa, slightly less than the difference in the medians. Hence, numerical consideration of the quantiles supports the visual assessment that bone china is stronger than hard porcelain, although with considerable overlap of strengths. In even greater detail, the peak strength mean \pm standard deviation values for bone china and hard porcelain are (91.2 ± 37.9) MPa and (72.3 ± 34.7) MPa, respectively. Using the N values given, a Student’s t -test gives a probability value of $p = 0.0178$ for equality of the mean peak strength values. Hence, at the conventional $p = 0.05$ level, the mean peak strength values are significantly different—bone china is stronger than hard porcelain

(a statement made much earlier, Dinsdale 1961).

Two other comparisons provide useful contrasts. The mean \pm standard deviation failure strain values for bone china and hard porcelain are $(1.17 \pm 0.49) m\epsilon$ and $(1.05 \pm 0.51) m\epsilon$, respectively. A Student's t -test gives a probability value of $p = 0.2592$ for equality of the mean failure strain values. At the conventional $p = 0.05$ level, the mean failure strain values are not significantly different. In a more straightforward materials comparison, the peak strength 50 % quantile of aluminous porcelain is 136 MPa and the difference between the 83 % and 17 % quantiles is 91 MPa. Thus, the difference with the median strength of hard porcelain is 71 MPa and the average half-span for both is 35 MPa, much less than the median difference. The peak strength mean \pm standard deviation value for aluminous porcelain is (137.9 ± 43.2) MPa. In this case a Student's t -test gives a probability value of $p < 0.0001$ for equality of the mean strength values of aluminous porcelain and hard porcelain. Hence, at the conventional $p = 0.05$ level the mean values are significantly different—aluminous porcelain is much stronger than hard porcelain (a statement also made earlier, Austin et al. 1946).

4.2 Flaws

The previous section considered the strengths of bone china and hard and aluminous porcelain with little regard (except for density ρ) to the physical strengthening mechanisms acting in the materials; that is, with little regard to the strength controlling flaws. The effects of flaws on porcelain strength are now considered, providing insight to strength variability and a foundation for subsequent development of a fracture mechanics model of porcelain strength.

A guiding principle in considering the effects of flaws on brittle fracture strength is the Griffith equation,

$$\sigma = T/\psi c^{1/2}, \quad (1)$$

where σ is the strength of a stressed component. The component material is characterized by toughness T . The strength controlling flaw is characterized by crack length c and a dimensionless factor ψ related to the nature of the flaw. ψ is of order unity and characterizes, for example, the proximity of the crack to a free surface, whether the crack front is straight or curved, whether the crack is associated with a pore or an included particle, or whether the crack is affected by a residual stress field associated with a contact or microstructural inhomogeneity. In all cases, strength σ increases as material toughness T increases, and decreases as flaw size c and flaw potency ψ increase. As strength controlling flaws in brittle materials are usually imposed by extrinsic machining processes and contact events, most brittle materials do not have well defined strengths. However, if a materials fabrication process determines material toughness *and* the strength controlling flaw characteristics then an intrinsic strength can be associated with the material. This was the implicit assumption in the previous section. Some details of that assumption regarding flaw characteristics are reviewed here. Specifically, details of strength variations associated with two fabrication-controlled microstructural features—porosity and included particles—are considered. The Griffith equation provides a means of estimating the likely effects of these microstructural features.

Porosity of a material is usually specified as a relative pore volume, V_P , characterized as open, closed, or total porosity. Open porosity allows fluid exchange with the environment external to a component and is most often determined from component mass measurements in dry and fluid saturated states. Closed porosity does not allow fluid exchange with the environment and is most often determined from mass measurements in the dry state and suspended in a fluid. This latter measurements are an extension of the “Archimedes”

method used above in the specification of density ρ : closed porosity is given by $1 - \rho/\rho_0$, where ρ_0 is the theoretical density of a material. Total porosity is the sum of open and closed porosity and is most often determined by stereological analysis of material sections but can be determined by component mass and external dimensions. Here, relative porosity V_P is applied in characterization of strength variations, with the recognition that all three porosity measures are used. Closed porosity typically dominates total porosity at small values, $V_P \leq 5\%$, and open porosity typically dominates at large values, $V_P \geq 20\%$. Whatever the form, increased V_P is expected to decrease strength as porous regions contribute zero to material fracture resistance and thus decrease T . In addition as V_P increases the probability of an included large pore, radius R , increases. If fabrication leads to invariant c/R , then c increases. If fabrication leads to invariant c , then ψ increases (particularly for open porosity). In both cases strength decreases. Hence, the combined effects of toughness decrease and increased flaw size and potency lead to an expectation that strength will decrease more rapidly than linearly with increased porosity.

The quantity of particles incorporated into a material is usually specified as a relative mass fraction prior to fabrication. In addition, pre-fabrication particle composition and size distributions are often determined by chemical, sieving, or optical techniques. It is usually intended that the particles are more robust than the developing matrix such that these particle characteristics are not too altered by the fabrication process. Hence, small added mass fractions of particles are expected to increase strength as particle fracture resistance is greater than that of the matrix (otherwise they would not remain as particles). If fracture paths on failure pass through included particles T is increased. If fracture paths are deflected to pass around particles ψ is decreased. If cracks are associated with the particle-matrix interface, increasing the particle mass fraction will eventually lead to particle-related flaws that are larger than other, pre-existing flaws. Further increases in the added mass fraction will decrease the strength as the probability of a large particle increases and thus c increases. Hence, particle additions are expected to lead to strength variations that exhibit maxima as functions of particle mass fraction.

Figure 14 is a semilogarithmic plot of strength σ as a function of porosity V_P . The upper filled symbols indicate the behavior of two polycrystalline ceramic materials and the lower open symbols indicate the behavior of several hard porcelain materials. The fine solid lines indicate empirical exponential decreases in strength with porosity, $\sigma \sim \exp(-bV_P)$ (Ryshkewitch 1953; Cook 2023) with $b = 10$. The strength observations for hard porcelain are mostly concentrated in the porosity domain $V_P < 0.1$ for which a decrease in strength is discernible although somewhat masked by experimental scatter. The observation suggests that microstructural factors other than porosity may be influencing strength. Despite the experimental scatter the expectation that strength should decrease more rapidly than linearly within a broad porosity domain is fulfilled for porcelain. The strength decrease is consistent with that of other ceramics.

Figure 15 shows plots of strength as functions of added particle mass fraction for (a) hard porcelain including quartz particles and (b) aluminous porcelain including alumina (corundum-based) particles. The results for different materials and fabrication processes are indicated by different sets of symbols and connecting lines. The upper set of symbols for hard porcelain clearly exhibits a maximum, in accordance with the expectation described previously. The gray line is a guide to the eye highlighting this trend. The other observations for hard porcelain display less well developed maxima. The upper set of symbols for aluminous porcelain exhibit a weak maximum at a very large fraction of particles. The gray line from a is repeated in b and emphasizes this behavior. The other observations for aluminous porcelain display the expected increase in strength at small particle fractions.

As might be anticipated from Figure 14, included particles influence the development of porosity such

that it is often difficult to distinguish particle and porosity effects on strength. Figure 16a shows a plot of the variations in density with fabrication temperature for hard porcelain materials, similar to Figure 3. In this case, however, the materials are distinguished by the inclusion of quartz particles of various sizes, represented by different fine connecting lines. The response of the material with the smallest particles is indicated by open symbols and displays a maximum density at 1300 °C similar to Figure 3. The responses of the materials with larger particles are indicated by the bold arrowed line. The response of the material with the largest particles is indicated by filled symbols and displays no clear maximum. As density is a (negative) measure of closed porosity it is clear that including larger particles leads to a greater volume of closed porosity that is only eliminated at higher fabrication temperatures. Figure 16b shows a plot of the variations in water absorption with fabrication temperature for a different set of hard porcelain materials. Note the inverted absorption scale. As before, the materials are distinguished by the inclusion of quartz particles of various sizes, represented by different fine connecting lines. The response of the material with the smallest particles is indicated by open symbols and displays an almost complete absence of absorption from 1200 °C to 1400 °C. The responses of the materials with larger particles are indicated by the bold arrowed line. The response of the material with the largest particles is indicated by filled symbols and displays absorption over the full domain of fabrication temperatures with a minimum at 1400 °C. As absorption is a (negative) measure of open porosity it is clear that including larger particles leads to greater open porosity that is only eliminated at higher fabrication temperatures. Hence, discerning particle size effects on strength requires minimization of the particle-porosity linkages shown in Figure 16. In practice, as implemented here, this requires strength measurements on materials fabricated to peak density: The fabrication temperature is adjusted for different particle sizes so as to effectively eliminate open and closed porosity (attaining the rectangles in Figure 12).

5 Observations: Particles

The sizes of particles retained, or created, in bone china and hard porcelain matrices during fabrication have long been regarded as critical in determining the strengths of these materials (e.g. Fritz 1937). Reviews of the then-contemporary ideas are given in Mattyasovszky-Zsolnay (1957) and Warshaw and Seider (1967) and a compilation of particle-related strengthening theories is given in Carty and Senapati (1998). Most attention has focused on particles in hard porcelain. An early hypothesis (taught to the current author as an undergraduate) was that observed clusters of interlocking mullite needles (e.g. Bernasconi et al. 2011), formed from the eutectic melt on fabrication, were responsible for enhanced porcelain fracture resistance (presumably in the manner of visually similar whisker composites). In terms of the Griffith equation introduced previously the mullite needles lead to an increase in T and thus enhanced strength. Mattyasovszky-Zsolnay (1957) and Kobayashi et al. (1992) have shown that this hypothesis cannot be completely correct as strengths are observed to be independent of mullite content (or mullite forming raw components) and mullite fractures more easily than the matrix (Ranachowski et al. 2013).

It was also long recognized that the peripheries of quartz particles retained on fabrication were often fractured and were responsible for porcelain strength degradation—such cracks are now known as “spontaneous microcracks.” In terms of the Griffith equation larger particles lead to an increase in c and thus decreased strength. [An ancillary point is that smaller particles are more easily dissolved in the matrix melt on fabrication and lead to greater densification (Ichiko et al. 1977b), greater toughness T , and thus increased strength.] The origin of the microcracks is the coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) mismatch between retained quartz particles and the glassy matrix. On cooling the particles and their peripheries are placed

in tension that often leads to circumferential cracking of the particle-matrix interface and the surrounding matrix (Li and Bradt 1993). Images of cracking at (and within) quartz particles in hard porcelain after fabrication are shown in many works (Warsaw and Seider 1967; Soma et al. 1980; Kirchoff et al. 1982; Fridez et al. 1982; Kobayashi et al. 1991, 1994a; Hamano et al. 1991ab, 1992; 1993; Kilikoglou et al. 1995; Carty and Senapati 1998; Ohya et al. 1999; Iqbal and Lee 2000; Ece and Nakagawa 2002; Bragança and Bergmann 2004, 2005; Bragança et al. 2006ab; De Noni et al. 2010b; Chmelík et al. 2011; Tunçel and Özel 2012; Akatsu et al. 2020), and at corundum in aluminous porcelain (Ramaswamy et al. 2005).

Figure 17 shows a plot of acoustic emission arising from such cracking on cooling during porcelain fabrication, using data derived from the published work. The acoustic emission is shown as a function of temperature by fine lines indicating the peak temperature attained prior to cooling. Two important displacive phase transition temperatures for SiO_2 polymorphs are indicated by dashed lines: the quartz α - β transition at 573 °C and the cristobalite α - β transition at $\approx 220^\circ\text{C}$. The $\beta \rightarrow \alpha$ transformations on cooling involve considerable structural contractions in both cases: volume strains of ≈ -0.01 . Acoustic emission behavior for each peak temperature is shown as values scaled to the acoustic emission rate at the cristobalite α - β transition temperature. The behavior for the peak temperature of 670 °C is shown in bold. On cooling from this temperature, the acoustic emission displays two clear peaks: one at temperatures slightly less than 573 °C and the other at temperatures slightly less than 220 °C.

The interpretation is that fracture and other disruptions to the matrix and particle-matrix interface caused by volume changes associated with the $\beta \rightarrow \alpha$ phase transformations lead to phonon emission. The undercooling arises from continued CTE effects after the phase transformations. The effects of the cristobalite transformation are observed over a broader temperature range than the quartz transformation, probably as a consequence of a broader range of particle sizes and transition temperatures. For peak temperatures less than 573 °C only the effects of the cristobalite transformation, similar to those of the 670 °C effects, are observed. For peak temperatures greater than 670 °C, approaching the usual fabrication temperature of hard porcelain, the acoustic emission peak associated with the quartz transformation increases in intensity and broadens significantly and moves to a greater degree of undercooling. The broadening effectively subsumes a clear cristobalite peak. The implication is that disruption to material microstructure, probably microcracking, is extensive. The microcracking is associated with the quartz $\beta \rightarrow \alpha$ phase transformation and CTE mismatch between the quartz particles and glassy matrix. [Acoustic emission interpreted as microcracking can also be induced by applied stress (see Appendix, Figure A3).]

In more detail, the volume thermal expansivities $\alpha = (1/V)\partial V/\partial T$ (here T is temperature) of quartz, cristobalite, corundum, and the glassy matrix are $\approx 33 \times 10^{-6} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$, $\approx 60 \times 10^{-6} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$, $\approx 24 \times 10^{-6} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$, and $\approx 3 \times 10^{-6} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$, respectively. Hence, assuming a softening temperature of the glass as $\approx 750 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, the thermal volume strain mismatches on cooling, $\Delta\alpha\Delta T$, for quartz and corundum in the glassy matrix are $\approx -22 \text{ m}\epsilon$ and $\approx -16 \text{ m}\epsilon$, respectively. The volume strains on phase transformation for quartz and cristobalite are $\approx -5 \text{ m}\epsilon$ and $\approx -50 \text{ m}\epsilon$, respectively. Hence upper bounds, assuming elastic responses relative to free particles, for the longitudinal strains (volume strains/3) in embedded quartz and corundum particles after fabrication, are ≈ 5 – $10 \text{ m}\epsilon$ (cristobalite would be greater).

Such bounds are observed, as shown in Figure 18, which is a plot of (longitudinal) strain measured in post fabrication particles as a function of particle size, using data derived from the published works cited. There are increasing and decreasing trends with particle size suggesting that matrix relaxation was a significant, particle-size dependent, factor in determining particle-matrix strain mismatch. Nevertheless, Figures 17 and 18 provide clear support for the effects of transformation and CTE based strains in determining the

mechanical state of porcelain microstructures (also the bulk CTE, Inoue et al. 1992; Bernasconi et al. 2011). The comparable values of the strains in Figures 18 and 13b imply that such fabrication strains must influence failure strains. This interaction is seen more clearly in comparison of the normal stresses within quartz and corundum particles in porcelain. Assuming a characteristic measured residual strain of $2 \text{ m}\epsilon$ from Figure 18, these stresses are $\approx 75 \text{ MPa}$ and 400 MPa for quartz and corundum, respectively, and comparable to, or greater, than the observed strengths, as shown in Figure 13a. Further, the normal matrix stresses developed in reaction to the particle strains, assuming particle volume fractions of 0.25, are $\approx -25 \text{ MPa}$ and -130 MPa . These values give support to the idea that compressive stresses developed in porcelain matrices affect crack propagation and that particles small enough to generate stress but suppress cracking could increase strength through generation of matrix compression (Mattyasovszky-Zsolnay 1957).

Figure 19 shows logarithmic plots of the observed variations in post-fired strength σ as a function of included particle size D for (a) hard porcelain containing quartz particles and (b) aluminous porcelain containing corundum particles, using data derived from the published works cited. Note that the strength axes are drawn to different scales. The dashed lines are guides to the eye of slope $-1/2$, $\sigma \sim D^{-1/2}$. Symbols represent mean values of reported strengths and lines connecting symbols are guides to the eye; where available, uncertainties are indicated as bars. In both materials, the strength decreases with increasing particle size and the behaviors of representative systems are indicated in bold. There are several points to note: At small particle sizes for both types of material, strengths do not decrease very rapidly with increasing particle size and in some cases appear almost invariant. At large particle sizes for hard porcelain, strengths decrease somewhat more rapidly than $D^{-1/2}$. For both types of material, there is considerable variation in the magnitude of the strength response between individual systems. All three of these points indicate significant effects of microstructure on fracture and thus on crack propagation and component strength. The following section develops fracture mechanics models of particle size effects on porcelain strengths.

6 Fracture Mechanics Models of Porcelain Strength

6.1 Microstructural Effects

The model developed here for porcelain strengths follows closely those developed for the strengths of free particles after impacting a surface (Cook 2023) and the strengths of components containing indentation flaws (Cook 2025 and references therein). As in those models the model for porcelain strength is based on the effects of porcelain microstructure on crack propagation at different length scales.

A schematic diagram of a porcelain microstructure is shown in Figure 20. The matrix of the material is a silicate glass containing a small amount of precipitated crystalline phases, typified by mullite whiskers. The matrix contains a large amount of a crystalline phase in the form of included particles (shown shaded). The particles are quartz in hard porcelain and corundum in aluminous porcelain. The characteristic dimension of the particles is diameter D , typically $D \approx 10 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$. The volume fraction of particles in the matrix is V_f , typically $V_f \approx 0.25$. The characteristic separation of the particles is $D(1 - V_f)/V_f$ and thus typically $\approx 30 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$. The characteristic normal stress in the particles is σ_D , typically $\sigma_D \approx 150 \text{ MPa}$. The reaction normal stress in the matrix to attain mechanical equilibrium is $-\sigma_D V_f / (1 - V_f)$, typically -50 MPa . It is emphasized that these values are characteristic average values for a microstructure and that considerable spatial heterogeneity, particularly in the orientation and magnitude of the principal normal stresses, is present as a consequence of variations in particle size, shape, and separation.

Strength analysis begins with consideration of fracture at various length scales, focusing on matrix fracture. The toughness T of the matrix is the invariant value T_0 , set by the chemistry of the silicate glass, any precipitated phases and porosity, and any reaction with atmospheric moisture. Typically $T_0 \approx 0.5 \text{ MPa m}^{1/2}$. Figure 21 shows schematic diagrams of matrix fracture at increasing scale: (a) at a single particle, (b) including many particles, and (c) at the scale of the component. In Figure 21a, a crack, length c , is shown in the matrix adjacent to a particle. The stress field acting on the crack in the matrix is a radially tensile field arising from the strained particle (Selsing 1961). The stress-intensity factor (SIF) K acting on the particle-localized crack, K_D , is

$$K_D = \chi \sigma_D D^2 / c^{3/2}, \quad (2)$$

where χ is a dimensionless geometry factor, of order unity, that takes into account the shape and location of the crack and the shape of the particle. The equilibrium condition for a fracture system is $K = T$ such that in this case

$$\chi \sigma_D D^2 / c^{3/2} = T_0. \quad (3)$$

Hence for a crack generated adjacent to a particle in a porcelain matrix on cooling from the fabrication temperature, inversion of Eq. (3) gives the stable equilibrium crack length c_0 as

$$c_0 = (\chi \sigma_D / T_0)^{2/3} D^{4/3}. \quad (4)$$

There are several points to note regarding Eq. (4). First, c_0 is a stable crack length as the SIF K_D is stabilizing: $dK_D/dc < 0$. Hence, cracks will remain at length c_0 under transient perturbations, such as small mechanical vibrations and thermal fluctuations. Second, c_0 has a stronger than linear dependence on particle size. Spontaneous microcracks such as these increase in size very rapidly as particle size is increased, in accord with the many observations in the works cited. Third, simple modification of Eq. (2) can describe other microcracks. In particular, circumferential microcracks trapped at the particle-matrix interface can be described by extending χ to include a dependence on relative crack size, c/D , and interpreting T_0 as an interface toughness. [An implicit fourth point is that Eq. (4) does not address the details of crack initiation, see Cook 2023, 2025.]

In Figure 21b, a crack, length c , is shown extending in the matrix after initiating adjacent to a particle. The crack is assumed have an approximately circular front, such that crack area $\sim c^2$. The stress field acting on the extended crack is predominantly compressive, modeled here (and earlier, see detailed descriptions in Cook 2023, 2025) as a compressive line force of magnitude f^* (force/length) acting at a distance δ behind the crack front. The (f^*, δ) combination describes microstructural effects acting on the propagating crack. Such effects include the overall compressive matrix field and dissipative crack path features such as ligamentary bridges and frictional interlocks arising as a consequence of crack path deviations in the heterogeneous multi particle stress field. The SIF acting on the extended crack arising from the microstructural interactions, K_μ , is

$$K_\mu = -\mu f^* \delta^{-1/2} [1 - (\delta/c)^{3/2}] \quad c \geq \delta, \quad (5)$$

where μ is a dimensionless geometry factor of order unity that takes into account the shape of the crack. The line force and length scale parameters f^* and δ scale with microstructural features as

$$f^* \sim \sigma_D D V_f / (1 - V_f), \quad (6)$$

the reaction stress, and

$$\delta \sim D(1 - V_f)/V_f, \quad (7)$$

the interparticle spacing. For short cracks there is no microstructural interaction and $K_\mu = 0$ for $c \leq \delta$. In the long crack limit $c \gg \delta$, K_μ approaches an invariant value ΔK ,

$$K_\mu \rightarrow \Delta K = -\mu f^* \delta^{-1/2} \sim -\sigma_D D^{1/2} V_f^{3/2} / (1 - V_f)^{3/2}, \quad (8)$$

characterizing a steady state restraining action of the microstructure on fracture. Note for small V_f that $|\Delta K| \sim V_f^{3/2}$, a much stronger dependence than simple intersection of particles gives for toughness, $T \sim V_f^{1/2}$ as discussed above. Microstructural interactions are much more effective than rule-of-mixtures.

In Figure 21c, a crack of arbitrary length c is shown propagating in a component under the influence of an applied tensile stress σ_A . The SIF acting on the crack in this case, K_A , is

$$K_A = \psi \sigma_A c^{1/2}, \quad (9)$$

where ψ is a dimensionless geometry factor of order unity that takes into account the coupling of the crack to the applied stress (and is most affected by the proximity of the crack to free surfaces). Note that K_A is destabilizing: $dK_A/dc > 0$. Hence, increased values of σ_A will ultimately lead to an unstable fracture system and component failure. The stress at which this occurs is the maximum sustainable stress or strength of the component.

The total SIF K_{tot} acting on the crack is the sum of Eqs. (2), (5), and (9):

$$K_{\text{tot}} = K_A + K_D + K_\mu. \quad (10)$$

Fracture equilibrium is given by $K_{\text{tot}} = T_0$, leading to

$$\psi \sigma_A c^{1/2} + \chi \sigma_D D^2 / c^{3/2} - \mu f^* \delta^{-1/2} [1 - (\delta/c)^{3/2}] = T_0. \quad (11)$$

Equation (11) can be rewritten by introducing the variables

$$D_*^2 = \mu f^* \delta / \chi \sigma_D \quad (12)$$

and

$$T_\infty = T_0 + \Delta T, \text{ where } \Delta T = -\Delta K. \quad (13)$$

D_* is a particle size scale that separates fracture systems with varying microstructural toughening effects (small particles) from those with invariant microstructural toughening effects (large particles). T_∞ is a steady state toughness level that pertains at long crack lengths. Note that the steady state negative microstructural interaction is then interpreted as a positive steady state toughening effect. Fracture equilibrium is then written as

$$\psi \sigma_A c^{1/2} + \chi \sigma_D (D^2 + D_*^2) / c^{3/2} = T_\infty. \quad (14)$$

This equation has the same form as that for indentation flaws in stressed components of materials exhibiting microstructural effects (Cook 2025) and is solved identically. The strength σ_m of a porcelain component

limited by included particle size in this case is thus

$$\sigma_m = \sigma^*[1 + (D/D_*)^2]^{-1/3}, \quad (15)$$

where the characteristic strength σ^* is given by

$$\sigma^* = T_\infty(T_\infty/\sigma_D D_*^2)^{1/3}(3/4^{4/3}\psi\chi^{1/3}). \quad (16)$$

For a porcelain containing very small particles, the strength tends to an invariant value

$$\sigma_m \rightarrow \sigma^* \quad D \ll D_*. \quad (17)$$

For a porcelain containing very large particles, the strength tends to a decreasing asymptote

$$\sigma_m \rightarrow \sigma^*(D/D_*)^{-2/3} \quad D \gg D_*, \quad (18)$$

noting the reciprocal effects of toughness variation and strength invariance and vice versa in D domains either side of D_* . [Indentation strength behavior is similar (Cook 2025). See Appendix, Figure A4, for a soft porcelain example.] Note that in the large particle limit that combining Eq. (4) into Eq. (18) gives $\sigma_m \sim c_0^{-1/2}$ such that the Griffith equation, Eq. (1), is recovered. Setting $\mu = 0$ in Eq. (11) leads to a SIF formulation identical in form to that for an “ideal” indentation in an invariant toughness material (Cook 2025). The strength σ_0 of a porcelain component limited by included particle size with no ensuing microstructural toughening effects is

$$\sigma_0 = T_0(T_0/\sigma_D D^2)^{1/3}(3/4^{4/3}\psi\chi^{1/3}) \quad (19)$$

and thus

$$\sigma_0 = \sigma^*(T_0/T_\infty)^{4/3}(D/D_*)^{-2/3}. \quad (20)$$

Figure 22 shows a logarithmic plot of the strengths σ_m of the representative porcelain materials from Figure 19 as a function particle size D . Open symbols represent aluminous porcelain containing Al_2O_3 particles and filled symbols represent hard porcelain containing SiO_2 particles. The solid lines in Figure 22 are visual best fits of Eq. (15) to the data, treating σ^* and D_* as fitting parameters for each material. The parameters for aluminous porcelain are indicated by arrows. The fracture mechanics model of strength, culminating in Eq. (15), clearly describes the observed behavior for both materials. At small particle sizes, the strengths tend to particle size invariant plateaus. At large particle sizes, the strengths tend to decrease with particle size of slope $-2/3$, $\sigma_m \sim D^{-2/3}$.

Similar best fits, although not as extensive, were performed for all the materials and strength observations in Figure 19. σ^* and D_* were determined in each case. The data were then scaled to generate σ_m/σ^* and D/D_* sets for each material. Figure 23 shows a logarithmic plot of the resulting scaled strength vs scaled particle size behavior including all the data sets. The bold gray line represents Eq. (15) in scaled form and exhibits a strength plateau at small particle sizes and a strength decrease at large particle sizes. The two asymptotic responses are indicated by the fine solid lines, as is the transition particle size $D/D_* = 1$. It is clear that the strength model describes the effects of particle size on the range of porcelain strength behaviors over a factor of more than 10^3 in scaled particle size. The dashed line in Figure 23 represents scaled σ_0 from

Eq. (20) using a steady-state/base toughness ratio $T_\infty/T_0 = 5$, a value not uncommon for microstructurally toughened materials (Cook 2025). The important point to note is that none of the strength observations increase at small particle sizes to follow the trend set by the σ_0 behavior. The implication is that all strength controlling cracks in porcelain materials are significantly influenced by microstructural toughening effects. Figures 22 and 23 have much in common with those describing the effects of microstructure on the strengths of ceramic materials containing indentation flaws (Cook 2025). In experimental coordinates, Figure 22 enables comparison of the relative *magnitudes* of the strengths of individual materials. In scaled coordinates, Figure 23 enables assessment of the overall *behavior* of the strengths of a class of materials.

6.2 Flaw Size Distributions

An implication of the microstructure based strength analysis is that the strength distributions of particle containing porcelain materials should be narrow. As shown in Eq. (11) microstructural effects stabilize fracture thereby reducing strength variability associated with variations in strength controlling flaw size arising during fabrication. Figure 24 shows strength edf behavior for a number of (a) hard porcelain and (b) aluminous porcelain materials, using data derived from the published works cited. The width of such distributions is characterized by the ratio of the greatest and least observed strength, $\sigma_{\max}/\sigma_{\min}$. For most of the porcelain materials shown, this ratio is approximately 1.2. In only one case does the ratio approach 2, the value typical for most ceramic materials (Cook 2023). The edf results thus support the implication of the strength analyses. (The behavior of soft porcelain materials is similar to the porcelains shown here, see Appendix Figure A5.)

A more physically based interpretation of the strength distribution behavior is to convert the strength range ratio $\sigma_{\max}/\sigma_{\min}$ into a ratio characterizing the effective domain width of the strength controlling flaws c_{\max}/c_{\min} . Using the Griffith equation, Eq. (1), gives

$$c_{\max}/c_{\min} = (\sigma_{\max}/\sigma_{\min})^{-2}. \quad (21)$$

Figure 25 shows a plot of c_{\max}/c_{\min} calculated in this way for a representative group of brittle materials (Cook 2023) and porcelain materials using data from Figures 8, 9, 24, and A5. Symbols represent values determined for individual materials systems. Although there is considerable variability, the horizontal line is a guide to the eye of the typical response observed for brittle materials (Cook 2023). The responses of the porcelain materials are all much less than those observed for other ceramics, particularly so for hard porcelains. The disparate behavior in Figure 25 has two probable explanations: First, mechanical test specimens for other ceramic materials are mostly machined to size and shape (bend bars) such that the strength controlling flaws are material extrinsic sawing and grinding contact flaws. Mechanical test specimens for most porcelain materials are cast or extruded to shape in the green state and cut to length (for bend bars) in the fired shape. As a consequence, the strength controlling flaws in porcelain materials are mostly intrinsic to the material, as generated in the fired microstructure. Second, although microstructural effects are evident in many brittle material strengths (Cook 2025) the strength distributions in Figure 25 include those from glasses, glass ceramics, and fine-grained polycrystals (Cook 2023) with weak microstructural influences on fracture. Microstructural influences on fracture are clearly evident in porcelain materials, especially the quartz containing hard porcelains, such that crack stabilization is prevalent, reducing the effects of initial flaw size variability, as indicated in Eq. (17).

As inferred from the bounds of strength measurements, the domains of strength controlling flaw sizes in

porcelain materials are narrower than those of many other brittle materials. In more detail, the strength distributions can be used to discriminate between the flaw size distributions. Figure 26 shows edf plots for two aluminous porcelain materials, (a) and (b), and two hard porcelain materials, (c) and (d). The plots are ordered in decreasing strength. Symbols represent individual strength measurement, thus forming $Pr(\sigma)$ for each material. The line in each plot is a visual best fit to the $Pr(\sigma)$ observations by a cumulative distribution function (cdf) $H(\sigma)$. The form of $H(\sigma)$ used was the Kumaraswamy distribution, which is particularly suited to bounded distributions (Kumaraswamy 1980). The distribution is given in parametric form as

$$x = (\sigma - \sigma_{\min}) / (\sigma_{\max} - \sigma_{\min}) \quad (22)$$

$$H(x) = 1 - (1 - x^a)^b, \quad (23)$$

where a and b are empirical parameters. Despite some scatter, the fits well describe the data, which are approximately sigmoidal (a shape difficult to discern in Figure 24). The underlying crack length distribution is given by

$$H_c(x) = 1 - H(x) = (1 - x^a)^b, \quad (24)$$

(Cook 2023), where now x is expressed in terms of crack length

$$x = (c^{-1/2} - c_{\max}^{-1/2}) / (c_{\min}^{-1/2} - c_{\max}^{-1/2}), \quad (25)$$

using Eqs. (1) and (21). The advantage of an analytical representation for the strength and crack length distributions is that the representation are differentiable (numerically) with no scatter. This is important as the physically meaningful crack length probability density function (pdf) $h(c)$ is given by

$$h(c) = dH_c(c)/dc, \quad (26)$$

noting the change in variable. Figure 27 is a plot of the strength controlling crack length pdf variations $h(c)$ resulting from Figure 26, using the above analysis and $\psi = 1$ and $T = 1 \text{ MPa m}^{1/2}$. The pdf variations are labeled as in Figure 26. The two strongest aluminous porcelains (a and b) exhibit the smallest and narrowest flaw distributions. The two weaker hard porcelains (c and d) exhibit larger and broader flaw distributions. Note that porcelains b and c that overlap in strength exhibit overlapping flaw distributions. A simple interpretation of Figure 27 is that the larger flaws in the hard porcelains are associated with large quartz particles and that such flaws are absent in aluminous porcelains. Bone china has strengths intermediate to hard and aluminous porcelains and could thus be expected to exhibit intermediate flaw distributions, probably associated with large included crystals of β -TCP (Figure 1) (the volume thermal expansivity of β -TCP is $\approx 30 \times 10^{-6} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$).

7 Synthetic-Based Bone China

The previous sections have focused on the effects of physical aspects of post-fabrication microstructure (pores, particles) on hard and aluminous porcelain properties. Here, attention is turned to the effects of pre-fabrication chemical changes (composition) on the properties of bone china. In particular, the changes considered are the replacement of the natural bone ash ingredient with synthetic bone ash or the chemical equivalent. Natural bone ash is derived by calcining bones (usually cattle bones) to generate β -TCP [β -

$\text{Ca}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$] powder containing some Mg, Na, and C impurities. On exposure to H_2O during the formation of a green porcelain body, the β -TCP hydrolyzes to hydroxyapatite [HA , $3\text{Ca}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2 \cdot \text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$]. On heating during fabrication to $1200\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, the HA decomposes back into β -TCP and CaO, and H_2O is evolved. The CaO aids in the formation of anorthite ($\text{CaO} \cdot \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 2\text{SiO}_2$) and a eutectic silicate liquid that enables sintering. On cooling the final bone china microstructure consists of a silica glass containing crystals of β -TCP, anorthite, and mullite, as recognized in early works (Weyl 1941ab; St. Pierre 1954, 1955, 1956).

Consideration of this reaction scheme suggests that any source of HA that enables the formation of a eutectic silicate liquid at $1200\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and forms β -TCP and anorthite on cooling is a viable bone china ingredient. Hence, patents have been issued for synthetic, chemical, sources of HA and TCP for bone china fabrication (US 1981, China 1995 Patents) and for the use of fish bone ash in bone china (Japan 2014 Patent). Implicit in the importance of chemical content is that a standard for bone ash (NIST 1992) is certified for composition alone. Synthetic HA for use in soft porcelain-like bioimplant materials has also been demonstrated for some time (Monroe et al. 1971; Rao and Boehm 1974; Tadic and Epple 2003). Religious concerns regarding the use of animal-derived bone ash have been expressed (Zakaria and Haron 2014; Salleh 2017), for which synthetic HA in ceramics might be an alternative.

Of particular interest here is that several research groups have compared bone china fabricated using traditional calcined cattle bones with that fabricated using either synthetic bone ash (Ichiko, 1978a; Yeşilay et al. 2007; Zhang et al. 2016; Balasooriya and Pitawala 2021; Özbeck, K. 2004; Rincón-López et al. 2018; Kabakci and Capoglu 2022) or a substitute (Jeong et al. 2007; Rajabi Mashhadi and Naghizadeh 2022; Taskiran et al. 2005, 2006). Figure 28 shows the results of such comparisons as a logarithmic plot of a property value or structural characteristic of bone china fabricated using synthetic ingredients with that obtained for bone china fabricated using bone ash. Note that only direct comparison studies are included here. Different symbols indicate different properties or characteristics, plotted in the following experimental units: density (Mg m^{-3}); strength (MPa); optical translucency (Goodman 1950, %), transmittance (%), or chromatic lightness L^* ; CTE ($10^{-6}\text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$); elastic modulus (GPa); biological activity (cell viability); and composition (% β -TCP generated or β -TCP wt%). The solid line indicates ideal agreement. The shaded regions highlight the comparisons for three important and obvious properties or characteristics: density, strength, and optical performance. In all cases, however, there is clear agreement. [It is important to distinguish these bone ash synthetic substitution studies with studies that *add* components to bone china starting ingredients: MgO (Ichiko 1978b); porcelain scrap (Mukhopadhyay et al. 2011; Lee et al. 2011; Arasteh Nodeh 2017); white cement (Arastehnodeh and Saghii 2018); waste glass and spodumene (Carus and Bragança 2013ab); alumina (Zhang et al. 2015); sepiolite fibers (Ran et al. 2016); sepiolite fibers and substituted shellfish ash (Tian et al. 2018); palygorskite fibers (Zhang et al. 2019); nepheline syenite (Kabakci and Capoglu 2020). In these case, there was an intent to improve, not simply compare, properties.]

Figure 28 addresses question [3] stated previously: Can synthetic materials replace the bone in bone china? Simple inspection of the property correlations in Figure 28 suggests that the answer to this question is “yes.” In detail, the mean \pm standard deviation for the ratio of synthetic/bone ash properties is 1.05 ± 0.28 . Using the $N = 29$ pairs of property values, a Student’s t -test gives a probability value of $p = 0.7099$ for property ratios = 1. Hence, at the conventional $p = 0.05$ level, the property values are not significantly different—bone china fabricated using synthetic ingredients is identical to that fabricated using natural bone ash (a conclusion arrived at earlier, [characteristics] “not so markedly changed,” Ichiko 1978a; and anticipated even earlier, “one may reasonably begin to discuss the properties of the china in terms of the final products, viz., [β -TCP, anorthite, and glass], St. Pierre 1956).

8 Discussion and Conclusions

A conclusion to be drawn from the observations and analyses in this report is that porcelain materials derive their straightforward fabrication schemes and resulting superior mechanical properties through the pervasive actions of silicate liquids formed at high temperatures. Specifically, silicate melts generated as eutectics from porcelain base components form and encapsulate particles during fabrication. On cooling the resulting microstructures consist of glassy matrices including crystalline particles. The three major porcelain materials—hard porcelain, bone china, and aluminous porcelain—derive their different fracture properties from different particles encapsulated or formed by their melts. The three porcelains can be viewed as a progression in improved fracture properties: At an initial level the eutectic melts of all three porcelains improve fracture properties beyond those of earthenware and stoneware by enabling complete densification of components from the green state, eradicating open porosity in earthenware and closed porosity in stoneware. At the next level hard porcelain improves on the properties of the glass matrix alone by incorporating quartz particles that are stiffer, harder, and tougher than the matrix. In addition, on cooling the quartz particles contract more than the matrix, leading to stress generation and enhanced microstructural influences that increase fracture resistance. However, the stress generated also leads to particle related cracks and degrades the strength of the material. Bone china improves on the properties of the glass matrix further by incorporating β -TCP and anorthite particles that, although not as robust mechanically as quartz or generate as much stress, still provide increased fracture resistance through microstructural effects. The removal of quartz minimizes particle related cracking and thus leads to strength improvements and the change in composition lead to slight decreases in required fabrication temperatures. Finally, aluminous porcelain improves on the matrix properties considerably by incorporating corundum particles that are stiffer, harder, and tougher than quartz and contract less on cooling. Stress generation on cooling and microstructural influences lead to increased fracture resistance that is retained without particle related crack generation. The change in composition however requires the usual high temperature porcelain fabrication temperatures and corundum is a more expensive base component than quartz.

As a consequence of the liquid eutectics formed during hard porcelain and bone china fabrication, the exact chemical compositions of the starting ingredients and the exact temperature cycles implemented in fabrication are of little importance. Thus, hard porcelain and bone china have been fabricated in many locations around the world, using local ingredients and a range of fabrications schemes, generating materials that are comparable to those produced in China, Europe, and North America. A list of locations is given in the Appendix and includes Africa, Asia, and South America. A further implication of the formation of eutectic melts is that the source of bone ash, if used in bone china fabrication, is also likely to be of little importance. Bones from cattle, oxen, and horses have been used historically (Rado, 1969). In the studies considered here fishbone ash (Japan patent 2014), shellfish shell ash (Tian et al. 2018), pig bone ash (Jeong et al. 2007), and reindeer bone ash (Hortling et al. 1999) were all used in bone china fabrication with no indication of properties differences from that using cattle bones (e.g. Gouvêa et al. 2007, 2008, 2010, 2015). Consideration of the chemical reactions on firing, the demonstrated effects of included porosity and particle size, and experimental observations, here and historically, suggest that it is extremely unlikely that the presence of grass-fed cattle bones could affect bone china properties or could be detected by any method other than trace element analysis. The claim of Brown (2020) is unlikely.

In summary, the answers to all three questions posed in the introduction regarding bone china are “yes:”

1 real bone is used in the fabrication of bone china;

- 2] bone china is (usually) stronger than hard porcelain; and
- 3] bone china can be fabricated using synthetic ingredients.

Of necessity, in answering these questions the behaviors of hard and aluminous porcelains, as well as bone china, have been examined. The effects of fabrication temperature on density and elastic modulus as well strength have been reviewed, along with the effects of strength-controlling flaws such as porosity and included particles. A fracture mechanics model of porcelain strength was developed that is applicable generally to stressed particle containing systems. Here, the model was used to describe the behavior of hard and aluminous porcelain, but is applicable to bone china as well (there are currently insufficient data). Other aspects of porcelain behavior that are related to strength behavior, such as indentation fracture, non-equilibrium crack growth, and dielectric breakdown were also considered (see Appendix). In considering all this it is important to recognize key contributions made by several research groups, especially those of Ichiko (1970s), Kobayashi (1990s), Hamano (1990s), Lee (1990s–2000s), Bragança (2000s), and Zhang (2010s), and two key publications, of many, from *Journal of the American Ceramic Society*, Austin et al. (1946) and Warshaw and Seider (1967).

A clear opportunity for optimizing the mechanical properties of bone china and hard porcelain materials, and the mechanical performance of bone china and hard porcelain components, is the application of controlled flaw fracture techniques. The strengths of all the components considered here were controlled by flaws intrinsic to the components, either flaws arising from material microstructures (e.g. particles or pores) or flaws arising from component preparation (e.g. sawing or machining). Such “intrinsic” strengths can be very important for component designers. However, it is usually very difficult to know if or how such strengths will be degraded in service or if such strengths could be enhanced by different component preparation methods. In addition, such strengths provide materials developers and fabricators with difficulties in optimizing materials fabrication methods and the resulting microstructures. The difficulties in both cases arise from the fact that the strength measurements use uncontrolled flaws. If flaw size and potency is controlled, strength measurements become unambiguous measures of materials and component properties. The flaw most used in controlled flaw strength testing is the Vickers indentation contact, in which the size, shape, and location of the flaw are all controlled. In this way, intrinsic strengths, intrinsic flaw sizes, and toughness variations can all be determined and compared for different materials and components. Microstructural and nonequilibrium fracture effects can also be determined. An extensive work on the subject (Cook 2025) describes and demonstrates the myriad applications of the technique. In particular, the broad range of fabrication tools available for bone china and hard porcelain enable exquisite microstructural control. Bone china and hard porcelain could thus easily supplant polycrystalline alumina as the test material of choice for application of indentation-strength techniques in determination of microstructural effects on fracture.

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10 Appendix

Figure A1. See caption.

Figure A2. See caption.

Figure A3. Acoustic emission can be generated by mechanical loading of hard porcelain components. The acoustic signal is emitted by the initiation of microcracks associated with quartz particles in the porcelain matrix. Mechanical loading provides the applied stress necessary to cause crack initiation events (Cook 2023, 2025). Applying a force that increases linearly with time (a) until component failure leads to an increasing acoustic emission rate (b), presumably caused by crack initiation at increasing numbers of smaller and smaller particles. Applying a force that is static with time and less than the failure force (e) leads to rapidly decreasing acoustic emission rate, illustrated as a power law in (f). Applying a force that increases with time before peaking and relaxing to a static value (d) leads to a peaked acoustic emission response (e) that combines the attributes of b and f. See figure caption for data source.

Figure A4. Controlled flaw sharp indentation testing is the most common method of assessing the fracture properties of brittle materials (Cook 2025). The test is usually a two step procedure. In the first step, an indenter, usually a Vickers diamond square pyramid, is loaded onto a brittle material surface to a prescribed peak load P and then unloaded. The residual plastic deformation impression semi diagonal a is related to the hardness H of the material by

$$a = (P/2H)^{1/2}. \quad (27)$$

The SIF acting on cracks generated at the indentation K_P is

$$K_P = \chi P/c^{3/2}, \quad (28)$$

where χ is a dimensionless geometry factor, of order unity, that takes into account the shape and location of the crack and plastic deformation zone. Setting the equilibrium condition for the indentation fracture system as $K_P = T_{\text{air}}$ gives the stable equilibrium crack length as

$$c_{\text{air}} = (\chi P/T_{\text{air}})^{2/3}. \quad (29)$$

In the second indentation testing step, the indented material is loaded to failure and the peak stress, the strength, σ_m is measured. The equilibrium fracture condition for the indentation cracks during loading is

$$\psi \sigma_A c^{1/2} + \chi(P + P^*)/c^{3/2} = T_{\infty}. \quad (30)$$

This equation has the same form as that for particle related flaws in porcelain. The strength σ_m of the indented component is

$$\sigma_m = \sigma^* [1 + P/P^*]^{-1/3}, \quad (31)$$

where the characteristic strength σ^* is given by

$$\sigma^* = T_{\infty} (T_{\infty}/P)^{1/3} (3/4^{4/3} \psi \chi^{1/3}). \quad (32)$$

Figure A4a is a logarithmic plot of indentation fracture and deformation dimensions a and c as functions of

indentation load P for porcelain materials. Different symbols represent different materials. The fine lines are guides to the eye of slopes $1/2$ and $2/3$, describing the behavior of indentation contacts, $a \sim P^{1/2}$, and indentation cracks, $c \sim P^{2/3}$, Eqs. (27) and (29). The lines were plotted using values of $H = 6$ GPa and $(\chi/T_{\text{air}})^{2/3} = 20 \text{ } \mu\text{m N}^{-2/3}$ typical of silicate glasses. The limited data imply that indentation fracture in porcelain materials does not depend significantly on material type and is controlled by the properties of the silicate matrix. Figure A4b is a logarithmic plot of indentation fracture strength σ_m as a function of indentation load P for a soft porcelain material. Symbols represent mean strengths measured at the indentation loads indicated; bars indicate uncertainties. The shaded band indicates the mean and standard deviation limits of the “intrinsic” strength of unindented specimens. The bold line is a visual best fit to the data using Eq. (31) and setting σ^* as the intrinsic strength. The dashed line indicates the large indentation load asymptote. The similarities of Figures 22 and A4 are clear.

Figure A5. See caption.

Figure A6. The degradation of porcelain strength under exposure to mechanical load and wet conditions is a very real concern for high voltage electrical insulator stacks used in external environments (Liebermann 2002; Sanyal et al. 2020). Delayed failure tests are a means of assessing such degradation.

Figure A7. See caption.

Figure A8. See caption.

Figure A9. Electrical breakdown has much in common with brittle fracture (Garboczi 1988) and hence many of the phenomena observed for mechanical failure of porcelain are also observed for electrical failure. This commonality is evident in Figures A9, A10, and A11, which are analogous to Figures 5, 14, and 24, respectively.

Figure A10. See caption.

Figure A11. See caption. This Figure highlights the lack of correspondence between “low moment” properties, which average responses over an entire component, and “high moment” properties, which pick out an extreme response in a component. Density and elastic modulus are exemplar low moment properties and fracture strength and breakdown field are exemplar high moment properties.

Location

Porcelains have been fabricated using local ingredients in many locations around the world, including:

Hard porcelain

Algeria (Kitoumi and Harabi 2011)

Bangladesh (Mustafi et al. 2008)

Brazil (Bragança and Bergmann 2004, 2005, 2009; Bragança et al. 2006ab; Souza et al. 2006)

Ethiopia (Merga et al. 2019)

India (Dana et al. 2004; Dana and Das 2004; Das et al. 2013)

Italy (Rambaldi et al. 2007)

Japan (Hamano et al. 1992, 1993; Kobayashi et al. 1991, 1992; Kubuki et al. 2010)

Korea (Katsuki et al. 2019, 2020; Kim et al. 2011)

Malaysia (Yahya et al. 2018)

Nigeria (Ezenwabude and Madueme 2015; Nwachukwu and Lawal 2018; Jamo et al. 2019; Toluwalope et al.

2015; Owoeye et al. 2019)
Spain (Martín-Márquez et al. 2009)
Turkey (Ozturk and Gultekin 2015)
Uganda (Olupot et al. 2006, 2008, 2010ab)

Bone china

Bangladesh (Mostari et al. 2017, 2018)
Brazil (Gouvêa et al. 2007, 2008, 2010, 2015; Miyahara et al. 2007)
Finland (Hortling et al. 1999)
Korea (Jeong et al. 2007)
Iran (Abou Elmaaty et al. 2022)
Iraq (Alhindawi and Tweej 2017)
Nigeria (Toludare et al. 2019)
Sri Lanka (Balasooriya and Pitawala 2021; Chandrakumara et al. 2021)

11 Table

Table 1. Observed Porcelain Characteristics

Characteristic	Quantile		
	Bone china 17, 50, 83	Hard porcelain 17, 50, 83	Aluminous porcelain 17, 50, 83
Fabrication temperature (°C)	1196, 1240, 1260	1201, 1280, 1340	1260, 1281, 1350
Density, ρ (Mg m ⁻³)	2.25, 2.52, 2.59	2.31, 2.42, 2.46	2.47, 2.59, 2.72
Young's modulus, E (GPa)	63.9, 77.7, 80.0	48.0, 68.5, 80.0	127.0, – , 144.0
Peak strength, σ (MPa)	54.0, 96.3, 121.1	45.0, 64.6, 92.0	84.1, 136.1, 175.0
Failure strain, ε_f (m ε)	0.85, 1.24 , 1.51	0.94, 0.94, 1.15	0.66, – , 1.22

– indicates insufficient data

m ε (milli strain) = 10⁻³

12 Figure Captions

12.1 Text Captions

Figure 1. Schematic diagrams of initial components, firing conditions, and resulting microstructures of [(a) and (b)] hard porcelain and [(c) and (d)] bone china. See Appendix, Figure A1, for similar diagrams for soft paste porcelain and aluminous porcelain.

Figure 2. Photograph of a road sign near Cowee NC indicating an historical origin of NC kaolin clay. The Cowee mound built by the indigenous Cherokee is a short distance through the woods beyond the sign (the mound is now protected). Source: M.L. Oyen.

Figure 3. Plots of fired density as a function of fabrication temperature for (a) hard porcelain and (b) bone china. Shaded bands are guides to the eye of temperature domain 1250–1300 °C. See Appendix, Figure A2, for similar plot for aluminous porcelain. Source: Data adapted from Monack and Smith 1933; Kobayashi et al. 1992; Iqbal and Lee 2000; Bragança and Bergmann 2003; Sánchez et al. 2006; Hamano et al. 1991a; Iqbal et al. 2000b; Zhang et al. 2015; Martins et al. 2021.

Figure 4. (a) Plot of observed peak density values as a function of fabrication temperature for bone china (filled symbols), hard porcelain (hatched symbols), and aluminous porcelain (open symbols). Bars indicate uncertainties where available. Rectangles delimit the 17 % and 83 % density and temperature quantiles for each material. (b) Plot of rectangular regions from (a). Source: Data adapted from Figure 3; Figure A2; and Ece and Nakagawa 2002; Bragança et al. 2006a; Bragança and Bergmann 2008; Olupot et al. 2008; Riahi Noori et al. 2007; Merga et al. 2019; Schroeder and Guertin 1978; Akatsu et al. 2020, 2021; Arastehnodeh and Saghi 2018; Dana et al. 2004a; Sane and Cook 1951; Bishai et al. 1985; De Noni et al. 2010a; Kim et al. 2011; Kitouni and Harabi 2011; Maity and Sarkar 1996; Ichiko 1976, 1977ab, 1978ab; Ichiko et al. 1978ab; Zhang et al. 2016, 2019; Carus and Bragança 2013ab; Kabakci and Capoglu 2020; Kara and Stevens 2002a; Mukhopadhyay et al. 2011; Kurita et al. 1999; Rajabi Mashhadi and Naghizadeh 2022; Yeşilay et al. 2007; Abou Elmaaty et al. 2022.

Figure 5. (a), (b), and (c). Plots of fired density and Young’s modulus as a function of fabrication temperature for hard porcelain. (d), (e), and (f). Trajectories of fired density and Young’s modulus on fabrication of hard porcelain from (a), (b), and (c), respectively. Source: Data adapted from (a) Kobayashi et al. 1992; (b) Sánchez et al. 2006; and (c) Gültekin et al. 2015; Gültekin 2018.

Figure 6. (a) Plot of observed peak modulus values as a function of peak density for bone china (filled symbols), hard porcelain (hatched symbols), and aluminous porcelain (open symbols). Bars indicate uncertainties where available. Rectangles delimit the 17 % and 83 % modulus and density quantiles for each material. (b) Plot of rectangular regions from (a). Source: Data adapted from Figure 5; and Koenig 1936; Rambaldi et al. 2007; De Noni et al. 2010ab, 2011; Chmelík et al. 2011; Aduda and Nyongesa 2000; Monack 1931; Tenorio Cavalcante et al. 2004; Batista et al. 2001; Esposito et al. 2005; Geller and Creamer et al. 1931; Carty et al. 2011; Martins et al. 2021; Ichiko 1976, 1978b, 1979; Ichiko et al. 1977ab; Kabakci and Capoglu 2020; Abou Elmaaty et al. 2022; Bribiesca Vázquez et al. 1988; Liebermann 2001a, 2017.

Figure 7. Logarithmic plot of Young’s modulus development as a function of density for bone china (filled symbols), hard porcelain (hatched symbols), and aluminous porcelain (open symbols). Bars indicate uncertainties where available. Rectangular regions are reproduced from Figure 6. Solid line is a guide to the eye of slope 3, $E \sim \rho^3$. Source: Figure 6.

Figure 8. Plots of strength as a function of peak firing temperature for (a) hard porcelain and (b) bone china. Shaded bands are guides to the eye of temperature domain 1250–1300 °C. Sources: Data adapted from Kobayashi et al. 1992; Ece and Nakagawa 2002; Bragança and Bergmann 2003; Sánchez et al. 2006; Ichiko 1978b; Zhang et al. 2015, 2016; Ballvé and Bragança 2010.

Figure 9. (a) Plot of observed peak strength values as a function of fabrication temperature for bone china (filled symbols), hard porcelain (hatched symbols), and aluminous porcelain (open symbols). Bars indicate uncertainties where available. Rectangles delimit the 17 % and 83 % strength and temperature quantiles for each material. (b) Plot of rectangular regions from (a). Source: Data adapted from Figure 4; Figure 8; and Latimer and Watts 1936; Avgustinik and Sintsova 1967; Ichiko 1976, 1978a, 1979; 1994; Ichiko et al. 1978a; Bragança and Bergmann 2008; Carus and Bragança 2013ab; Gouvêa et al. 2015; Eren et al. 2013; Kabakci and Capoglu 2020; Mukhopadhyay et al. 2011; Ran et al. 2016; Nasir et al. 2017ab; Tian et al. 2018; Toludare et al. 2019; Jeong et al. 2007; Rajabi Mashhadi and Naghizadeh 2022; Abou Elmaaty et al. 2022; Taskiran et al. 2005; Arastehnodeh and Saghi 2018; Dana et al. 2004; Bragança and Bergmann 2006; De Noni et al. 2010b; Sane and Cook 1951; Schroeder and Guertin 1978; Akatsu et al. 2020; Harada et al. 1996; Kobayashi et al. 1994a; Maity and Sarkar 1996; Riahi Noori et al. 2007; Warshaw and Seider 1967; Austin et al. 1946; Arasteh Nodeh 2017; Kim et al. 2011; Kubuki et al. 2010; Lee 1926; Loomis and Blackburn 1946; McDowell and Vachuska 1927; Morse 1948; Mustafi et al. 2008; Navias 1926, 1927; Olupot et al. 2010ab; Rambaldi et al. 2007; Smothers 1958; Tai et al. 2000; Thiess 1936; Toluwalope et al. 2015; Ustundag et al. 2006; Vukovich Jr 1956; Wilson and Koenig 1958; Yahya et al. 2018; Ozturk and Gultekin 2015; Riddle and Laird 1922ab; Carty and Pinto 2002; Carty et al. 2011; Boussak et al. 2015; Liebermann 2003.

Figure 10. Composite plot of peak strength σ empirical distribution functions $Pr(\sigma)$ (edf) for bone china, hard porcelain, and aluminous porcelain; different symbols represent different materials. Dashed lines indicated 17 % and 83 % distribution levels. Source: Figure 9.

Figure 11. (a) and (b). Plots of fired density and strength as a function of fabrication temperature for hard porcelain. (d) and (e). Trajectories of fired density and strength on fabrication of hard porcelain from (a) and (b), respectively. Source: Data adapted from Kobayashi et al. 1992; Ballvé and Bragança 2010.

Figure 12. Logarithmic plot of strength development as a function of density for bone china (filled symbols), hard porcelain (hatched symbols), and aluminous porcelain (open symbols). Bars indicate uncertainties where available. Rectangular regions are reproduced from Figure 9. Solid line is a guide to the eye of slope 3, $\sigma \sim \rho^3$. Source: Figure 4; Figure 9.

Figure 13. Plots of 17 % and 83 % quantiles for observed failure properties and density of bone china, hard porcelain, and aluminous porcelain. (a) Plot of rectangular regions indicating strengths and density

from Figure 9. (b) Plot of rectangular regions indicating failure strains and density using data from Figures 6 and 9. $1 \text{ m}\varepsilon = 10^{-3}$.

Figure 14. Semi-logarithmic plot of strength σ as a function of relative porosity V_P for macroscopic ceramic components (upper symbols) and hard porcelain (lower symbols). Solid lines are guides to the eye of negative exponential form, $\sigma \sim \exp(-10V_P)$. Source: Data adapted from Ryshkewitch 1953; Sane and Cook 1951; Duckworth 1951; Schroeder and Guertin 1978; Hamano et al. 1991ab.

Figure 15. Plots of strength as a function of added particle content for (a) quartz particles in hard porcelain and (b) alumina particles in aluminous porcelain. Symbols indicate measured mean strengths at the added particle mass fractions indicated; connecting lines are guides to the eye. Different symbol sets represent different materials and fabrication methods. The diagonal lines are guides to the eye and are common to a and b. Source: Data adapted from (a) Kobayashi et al. 1992, 1994a and (b) Austin et al. 1946.

Figure 16. Plots of (a) density (sensitive to closed porosity) and (b) water absorption (sensitive to open porosity) for hard porcelain systems as a function of fabrication temperature and included quartz particle size. Note inverted scale for b. Shaded bands are guides to the eye of temperature domain 1250–1300 °C. Fine lines indicate responses for different particle sizes; lines with symbols indicate response extremes. Bold lines with arrows indicate overall trends. Source: Data adapted from (a) Hamano et al. 1991a and (b) Warshaw and Seider 1967.

Figure 17. Plot of scaled acoustic emission as a function of temperature for hard porcelain. Lines indicate emission rates scaled to the value observed at at 220 °C for bodies cooled from the peak temperatures indicated. The quartz and cristobalite α - β transition temperatures are indicated as dashed lines. The bold line indicates the response for a peak temperature of 670 °C that encompasses both transitions. Source: Data adapted from Kirchhoff et al. 1982. Similar results were reported by Fridez et al. (1982), Ohya et al. (1999), and Chmelfk et al. (2011).

Figure 18. Logarithmic composite plot of measured strain in particle as a function of particle size for quartz (SiO_2) particles in hard porcelain and corundum (Al_2O_3) particles in aluminous porcelain. Symbols and fine connecting lines represent strains observed at specified particle sizes for individual studies. Bars indicate uncertainties where available. Source: Data adapted from Carty and Pinto 2002; Hamano et al. 1991a; Cucka and Oliva 1968.

Figure 19. Logarithmic plots of strength as a function of particle size for (a) quartz (SiO_2) particles in hard porcelain and (b) corundum (Al_2O_3) particles in aluminous porcelain. Open symbols and fine connecting lines represent strengths observed at specified particle sizes for individual studies. Bars indicate uncertainties where available. Solid symbols and bold connecting lines represent strengths observed at specified particle sizes for representative individual studies (Warshaw and Seider 1967; Hamano et al. 1991b; Harada et al. 1996). Dashed lines are guides to the eye of slope $-1/2$, $\sigma \sim D^{-1/2}$. Source: Data adapted from Warshaw and Seider 1967; Kobayashi et al. 1994a, 2000; Carty and Pinto 2002; Ece and Nakagawa 2002; Bragança et al. 2006b; Sánchez et al. 2006; Mustafi et al. 2008; Krause 1937, Floyd et al. 1967, Banda and Messer 1990, Weyl 1959 as cited by Kobayashi et al. 2000; Hamano et al. 1991b, 1992, 1993; Austin et al. 1946;

Mattyasovszky-Zsolnay 1957; Harada et al. 1996; Hettich et al. 2017.

Figure 20. Porcelain structure

Figure 21. Porcelain fracture mechanics model elements

Figure 22. Logarithmic plot of strength as a function of particle size for quartz (SiO_2) particles in hard porcelain (filled symbols) and corundum (Al_2O_3) particles in aluminous porcelain (open symbols). Solid lines are fits to the data of the microstructure-based fracture mechanics strength model; cf with bold solid lines in Figure 17. Note the small particle strength plateaus and large particle strength decreases and the particle size and strength transition parameters σ^* and D^* . Source: Data adapted from Warshaw and Seider 1967; Hamano et al. 1991b; Harada et al. 1996.

Figure 23. Logarithmic plot of scaled strength σ/σ^* as a function of scaled particle size D/D^* for quartz particles in hard porcelain and corundum particles in aluminous porcelain. Bold solid line indicates behavior predicted by the fracture mechanics strength model. Fine solid lines indicate asymptotes and transition scale. Note that the strength behaviors for all porcelain materials fall on a single scaled response. Source: Data adapted from Figure 19.

Figure 24. Empirical distribution function (edf) plots of strengths for (a) hard porcelain and (b) aluminous porcelain materials. Different sets of symbols represent different materials and studies. Source: Data adapted from Kubuki et al. 2010; Kobayashi et al. 1991, 1994a, 2003; Akatsu et al. 2020; Hettich et al. 2017; Soma et al. 1980; Carlström et al. 1986; Lamon and Evans 1983; Lamon 1988.

Figure 25. Plot of sample crack length ratios c_{\max}/c_{\min} inferred from strength distribution measurements of brittle materials and porcelains. Different sets of symbols represent different materials. It is clear that porcelain materials exhibit restricted domains of strength controlling cracks relative to other brittle materials. Source: Data adapted from Cook 2023; Figure 8; Figure 9; Figure 24; Figure A5.

Figure 26. Empirical distribution function (edf) plots of strengths for aluminous porcelain, (a) and (b), and hard porcelain, (c) and (d). Symbols represent individual strength measurements. Lines represent fits of Kumaraswamy bounded distribution functions. Note decreasing strength scales (a)–(d). Source: Data adapted from Kobayashi et al. 1994, 2003; Carlström et al. 1986; Akatsu et al. 2020.

Figure 27. Composite plot of strength-controlling crack length probability density functions for porcelain materials from Figure 26. Identifying labels abcd correspond to panels for different materials in Figure 26.

Figure 28. Logarithmic plot of comparative bone china characteristics and properties resulting from substitution in fabrication of bone ash by “synthetic” materials. Characteristics and properties include density (highlighted by lower shaded disc) and strength and reflectivity (highlighted by upper shaded disc). Symbols represent results observed for individual studies. Solid line represents ideal agreement. Source: Data adapted from Ichiko, 1978a; Yeşilay et al. 2007; Zhang et al. 2016; Balasooriya and Pitawala 2021; Özbeck, K. 2004; Rincón-López et al. 2018; Kabakci and Capoglu 2022; Jeong et al. 2007; Rajabi Mashhadi and Naghizadeh 2022; Taskiran et al. 2005, 2006).

12.2 Appendix Captions

Figure A1. Schematic diagrams of initial components, firing condition, and resulting microstructure of [(a) and (b)] soft paste porcelain, Belleek, and “dental porcelain” (the latter so called as the base glass frit is a feldspar composition close to that of the eutectic formed in true porcelains) and [(c) and (d)] aluminous porcelain.

Figure A2. Plot of fired density as a function of fabrication temperature for aluminous porcelain. Shaded band is a guide to the eye of temperature domain 1250–1300 °C. Source: Data adapted from Austin et al. 1946; Harada et al. 1996; Akatsu et al. 2020.

Figure A3. Plots of acoustic emission responses for hard porcelain components under the actions of applied forces. (a), (c), (e): schematic diagrams of force-time trajectories applied in experiments. (b), (d), and (f): observed acoustic emission rate responses, respectively (note logarithmic scale for f). Pair c,d is intermediate between pairs a,b and d,f. Source: Data adapted from Evans and Linzer 1973; Evans 1975. Similar results reported by Ranachowski et al. 2010.

Figure A4. Logarithmic plots of Vickers indentation contact behavior as functions of indentation load P for porcelain materials. (a) Indentation dimensions a and c . Different sets of symbols represent different materials and studies. Fine lines indicate ideal indentation fracture and deformation responses of slope $2/3$ and $1/2$, respectively ($c \sim P^{2/3}$, $a \sim P^{1/2}$). (b) Indentation strength σ . Shaded region indicates intrinsic (non-indented) strength. Dashed line indicates ideal indentation strength response of slope $-1/3$ ($\sigma \sim P^{-1/3}$). Bold solid line indicates response including microstructural effects. Source: Data adapted from Batista et al. 2001; Rizkalla and Jones 2004; Cesar et al. 2011; Anusavice et al. 1991; Ali 1993; Rosa et al. 2009.

Figure A5. Empirical distribution function (edf) plots of strengths for soft porcelain. Different sets of symbols represent different materials and studies. Source: Data adapted from Fairhurst et al. 1992; Tinschert et al. 2000; Fleming et al. 2000; Teixeira et al. 2007.

Figure A6. Semi logarithmic plots of delayed failure time t_f as functions of static applied stress σ_A for glass and porcelain materials in moist environments. Different sets of symbols represent different materials and studies. Bold lines indicate responses in air based on nonequilibrium fracture rates (Cook 2025). Note divergence in failure time at small applied stress levels—the threshold strengths. Source: Data adapted from (a) Baker and Preston 1946 and (b) Soma et al. 1980.

Figure A7. Semi logarithmic plot of crack velocities v as functions of mechanical energy release rate \mathcal{G} for porcelain materials in moist environments. Different sets of symbols represent different materials and studies. Bold lines indicate crack velocity responses in water based on nonequilibrium fracture principles (Cook 2025). Note vanishing responses at small mechanical energy release rates—the crack velocity thresholds—and depressed velocities at large \mathcal{G} values arising from moisture transport limitations. Source: Data adapted from Evans and Linzer 1973; Soma et al. 1980.

Figure A8. Semi logarithmic plot of scaled strengths, σ/σ_{\max} , as functions of applied stressing rate, $\dot{\sigma}_A$ —a dynamic fatigue plot—for soft porcelain materials. Different sets of symbols represent different studies. Bars indicate uncertainties. All data are scaled to the maximum (inert) strength σ_{\max} indicated on right. Bold line indicates fatigue response based on nonequilibrium fracture principles (Cook 2025). Note limiting relative strength at small stressing rates on left—the threshold strength. Fine lines indicate bounds based on inert strength dispersion. There is little distinction between soft porcelain materials; the responses are similar to those of silicate glasses. Source: Data adapted from Fairhurst et al. 1993; Teixeira et al. 2007; Morena et al. 1986; Hettich et al. 2017; Rosa et al. 2009; Carlström et al. 1986; Gonzaga et al. 2011.

Figure A9. Plots of (a) density, (b) (open) porosity, and (c) electrical breakdown field as functions of fabrication temperature for hard porcelain. Note clear correlation between breakdown field and porosity. Source: Data adapted from Monack 1931; Monack and Shardlow 1931; Monack et al. 1932; Monack and Smith 1933.

Figure A10. Semi-logarithmic plot of electrical breakdown field as a function of relative porosity V_P for hard porcelain. Solid line is a guide to the eye of negative exponential form, $\sigma \sim \exp(-10V_P)$. Plot scale and line are identical to Figure 14. Source: Data adapted from Monack 1931; Monack and Shardlow 1931; Monack et al. 1932; Monack and Smith 1933.

Figure A11. Empirical distribution function (edf) plots of (a) electrical breakdown field and (b) Young's modulus for hard porcelain materials. Plots are of same scale. Different sets of symbols in panel a represent different fabrication temperatures (lowest on left); representative set shown shaded and fit with bold straight line, fine lines are guides to the eye of same slope. Moduli shown in panel b encompass fabrication temperatures highlighted in panel a. Slope of bold line in panel b is repeated from panel a. Note lack of correspondence between breakdown and modulus dispersion. Source: Data adapted from Monack 1931; Monack and Shardlow 1931; Monack et al. 1932; Monack and Smith 1933.

Porcelain Strength: Figures Overview

February 2025

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Appendix

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Figure A8.

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Figure A11.